

ANIPH SSbD Framework/D2.3

WP2 ANIPH project baseline, T2.3. SSbD evaluation framework, design basis and production processes guiding

Authors: A. Matamoros (KVC), È. Dussault (KVC), M. Ferrando (KVC), M. Kotzabasaki (AUA), V. Anestis (AUA), & C. Maraveas (AUA)

Technical References

Project Acronym	ANIPH
Project Title	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
Project Coordinator	ASOCIACION EMPRESARIAL DE INVESTIGACION CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADOY DEL PLÁSTICO DE LA REGION DE MURCIA CETEC Carmen Fernández: c.fernandez@ctcalzado.org
Project Duration	January 2025 – December 2028 (48 months)

Deliverable No.	D2.3
Dissemination level*	PU - Public
Work Package	WP2 - ANIPH project baseline
Task	T2.3 - SSbD evaluation framework, design basis and production processes guiding
Lead beneficiary	KVC
Contributing beneficiaries	CETEC, AUA, GoPHA, UGR
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2025
Actual submission date	01 October 2025

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

V	Date	Comments	Author/Reviewer
V0	01/07/2025	First draft of document	A. Matamoros (KVC)
V1	12/09/2025	Revised version based on the comments of internal reviewer 1	A. Matamoros, È. Dussault (KVC) / M. Kotzabasaki, V. Anestis, C. Maraveas (AUA) / M. Nicolás Liza (CETBIO)
V2	24/09/2025	Revised version based on the comments of internal reviewer 2	A. Matamoros (KVC), È. Dussault (KVC) / M. Kotzabasaki (AUA), V. Anestis (AUA), C. Maraveas (AUA) / C. Blaya, C. Fernández (CETEC)
V3	24/09/2025	Revised version based on the comments of internal reviewer 3	A. Matamoros, È. Dussault, G. Munares, M. Ferrando (KVC)
VF	01/10/2025	Final version, approved by the project coordinator and submitted to EC	C. Blaya, C. Fernández (CETEC)

Contents

1. List of Abbreviations	6
2. Executive Summary	7
3. Introduction.....	8
4. Methodology: ANIPH SSbD Framework Design	10
4.1. SSbD framework overview	10
4.2. (Re)design phase: Guiding principles	12
4.3. Framework implementation.....	14
4.4. Assessment phase.....	15
5. Safety by Design and Safety Assessment.....	17
5.1. Design phase.....	17
5.2. Assessment Phase: Methodology	19
6. Environmental Sustainability by Design (eSbD) and eLCA	26
6.1. Design phase.....	26
6.2. Assessment phase: Methodology	28
7. Social Sustainability by Design (S-SbD) and S-LCA	34
7.1. Design phase.....	34
7.2. Assessment phase: Methodology – Social Life Cycle Assessment.....	37
7.3. Assessment phase: Methodology – Acceptability & Awareness.....	43
8. Sustainability Costing by Design (cSbD) and LCC	46
8.1 Design phase.....	46
8.2 Production process and LCC calculations	48
8.3 Assessment phase: Methodology	49
9. Evaluation and support decision tool	54
10. Conclusions.....	57
11. References	58

List of Tables

Table 1 SSbD design principles (based on [1]).....	12
Table 2 List of aspects (hazard properties) relevant for step 1 (taken from [1])	20
Table 3 Environmental sustainability principles.....	27
Table 4 Environmental impact categories assessed in ANIPH (adapted from [1])	30
Table 5 Key flows and examples of primary data requirements to conduct LCA within ANIPH foreground systems	31
Table 6 Functional units across environmental sustainability assessment domains.....	32
Table 7 Social sustainability principles (based on [33]) and the ANIPH project	35
Table 8 Relations between social sustainability aspects and principles (based on [33]).....	40
Table 9 Indicators for the S-LCA assessment and their relations to SDGs	41
Table 10 BBpPs acceptability assessment framework	44
Table 11 Summary of the dimensions, tools and methods, components, and stakeholders involved in the social sustainability assessment.....	45
Table 12 Economic sustainability principles (based on [9])	46
Table 13 ANIPH LCC indicators and related aspects and definitions (based on [9])	50
Table 14 Relations between economic sustainability aspects and principles (based on [9])	52

List of Figures

Figure 1 Hierarchical SSbD principles (based on [1]).....	10
Figure 2 Hierarchical SSbD concept definition (taken from [1]).....	13
Figure 3 Sequential implementation of working packages and their respective deliverables	14
Figure 4 Steps of the ANIPH SSbD assessment (adapted from [1]).....	15
Figure 5 ANIPH SSbD framework formulation & assessment (taken from [1]).....	16
Figure 6 Relations between the innovation process, design principles, and the SSbD assessment (taken from [9])	18
Figure 7 Illustration of chemical/material safety components captured in the proposed framework (taken from [1])	19
Figure 8 Relevant aspects of the exposure identification and assessment (taken from [9]).....	23
Figure 9 Aspects of the risk characterisation (taken from [9]).....	24

1. List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
A2C	Agro2Circular
BREF	Best available techniques reference
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulation
cSbD	Sustainability costing by design
DNEL	Derived no effect level
ECETOC	European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
eLCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
ES	Exposure scenarios
eSbD	Environmental sustainability by design
EUSES	European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances
GHS	Globally Harmonized System
GWP	Global warming potential
IAS	Intentionally added substances
ILO	International Labour Organization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
M	Month
ML	Machine learning
NAMs	New approach methodologies
NIAS	Non-intentionally added substances
oBL	Over the baseline
OELs	Occupational exposure limits
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PNEC	Predicted no effect concentration
QSAR	Quantitative structure–activity relationship
RMMs	Risk management measures
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
S-SbD	Social sustainability by design
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSbD	Safe and sustainable by design
TRA	Tiered Targeted Risk Assessment
TRL	Technology readiness level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work package
WTP	Willingness to pay

2. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D.2.3) presents the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework developed within ANIPH, including design principles and assessment criteria to ensure the safety and sustainability for the two expected use cases (i.e., wound dressings and their respective flexible packaging).

The work carried out included the review of existing EC guidelines, outcomes of previous EU projects, and recognised international recommendations. Based on this, a joint methodology was developed and applied across four dimensions: safety, and environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Unlike conventional frameworks that focus on safety and the environment, ANIPH's approach systematically addresses the social and economic sustainability dimensions as well.

Key findings are the following:

- For the safety and environmental dimensions, clear design principles and measurable indicators have been established, building on previous work carried out by the SSbD leaders (KVC) validated through different research projects (i.e., ViSS, Agro2Circular), and on well-established methodologies such as the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) framework. This includes the evaluation of both intentionally added substances (IAS) and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) and the quantification of environmental impacts throughout the entire life cycle using Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (eLCA).
- For the social and economic sustainability dimensions, a preliminary set of principles and indicators has been proposed. These remain more flexible, reflecting both the lack of universally agreed definitions and the early-stage nature of TRL of ANIPH technologies. Their validation will be pursued with experts in next stages. The approach for social sustainability (S-SbD) uses Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) and complementary metrics to evaluate impact on workers, value chain actors, society, local communities, and consumers. For economic sustainability (cSbD), the framework relies on Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to assess techno-economic feasibility and operational costs, even at early development stages.
- The framework combines design strategies (safety by design, resource efficiency, circularity, end-of-life considerations), applicable policies, and regulatory requirements to ensure alignment with EU standards.
- The SSbD assessment results will be integrated into a digital support tool (Evaluation and Decision tool) within the ANIPH ICT Platform. This tool will use a uniform scoring system (0 to 4, 2 being the passing score) to rank product options, facilitating data-driven decision-making.

The work led to the following main conclusions:

- The SSbD framework offers a structured approach to guide the safe and sustainable development of ANIPH materials and products.
- It highlights the maturity of safety and environmental sustainability indicators, while stressing the need for further expert input on social and economic sustainability criteria.
- The framework provides the foundation for evaluation and support tools to be used in later stages of the project, ensuring consistency across work packages.

3. Introduction

Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) is a pre-market approach to chemical, material, and product (re)design that ensures functionality while minimising harm to human health and the environment throughout the entire life cycle [1]. Following the Joint Research Centre (JRC) framework [1], SSbD integrates two complementary phases: a (re)design phase establishing guiding principles and criteria, and an assessment phase quantifying safety and sustainability (covering environmental, social, economic dimensions) performance across multiple dimensions. ANIPH advances novel PHA-based wound dressings (including probiotics@cellulose alternatives to antibiotics) and water barrier packaging from TRL 2-3 to TRL 4-5, addressing an existing gap by systematically integrating social and economic sustainability assessments into the standard SSbD framework. This approach responds to the recognised need for expanded SSbD methodologies that enable practical incorporation of all sustainability dimensions into innovation practice [2]. The specific aim of Deliverable D2.3 is to establish the SSbD framework that will guide the safe and sustainable development of ANIPH products.

The ANIPH SSbD framework builds upon established principles while extending methodological scope through incorporating the eight SSbD principles outlined in the JRC framework (i.e., material efficiency, hazardous chemical minimisation, energy efficiency, renewable sources, emission prevention, exposure reduction, end-of-life optimisation, and life cycle consideration; [1]) and introducing complementary social and economic design criteria validated through expert consultation. The assessment phase employs established methodologies—Life Cycle Assessment (LCA; [3]) and Product Environmental Footprint (PEF; [4]) for environmental evaluation, Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA; [5]) for social impact analysis along with other metrics, and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) with Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) for the economic sustainability assessment. The framework operates through an integrated ICT Platform comprising three interconnected tools: a Traceability tool for secure value chain information management, an Evaluation & Decision tool integrating the assessment matrix for evidence-based decision-making, and a public tool for transparent stakeholder communication of value chain impacts and performance.

D2.3 builds directly on the mapping of Information and Labelling Systems (ILS) conducted in Deliverable D2.2, ensuring alignment between SSbD indicators and the data requirements of existing standards, certifications and labelling schemes. In addition, the framework established here is designed to inform subsequent tasks and deliverables across the project, including those focused on production, testing, sustainability assessment, demonstration activities, and contributions to information, labelling and policy.

ANIPH's SSbD development follows three strategic milestones: 1) framework enhancement through validation of extended SSbD principles incorporating social and economic dimensions via expert panel consultation, building upon UNEP recommendations [5] and EU project insights; 2) methodological implementation involving systematic application of safety and sustainability assessments using validated indicators and methodologies, with environmental assessment conducted by AUA and social/economic evaluation by KVC in WP5, and WP11; and 3) decision support integration through development of a user-friendly dashboard facilitating holistic assessment interpretation and strategic decision-making based on comprehensive SSbD

performance data. The detailed framework design and methodology are presented in Section 4 *Methodology: ANIPH SSbD Framework Design*, where the SSbD methodology is presented before delving deeper into each dimension in the following sections: Section 5 deals with safety (*Safety by Design and Safety Assessment*), Section 6 with environmental sustainability (*Environmental Sustainability by Design (eSbD) and eLCA*) and Sections 7 (*Social Sustainability by Design (S-SbD) and S-LCA*) and 8 (*Sustainability Costing by Design (cSbD) and LCC*) deal with social and economic sustainability, respectively. Finally, a first reflection on the Evaluation and Support Decision tool is presented in Section 9. The deliverable closes with the *Conclusions* section, where the methodological limitations and next steps are presented.

4. Methodology: ANIPH SSbD Framework Design

4.1. SSbD framework overview

Building on the established JRC SSbD methodology [1], the SSbD approach is a voluntary framework developed by the European Commission (EC) to guide innovation toward safer and more sustainable chemicals and materials throughout their entire life cycle. It integrates risk assessment and sustainability assessment methodologies, emphasising iterative and tiered evaluations as data and knowledge evolve during the innovation process. It promotes the substitution of hazardous substances, the design of environmentally friendly processes, and the development of non-toxic material cycles, aligning with the European Green Deal [6] and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability [7]. It supports innovators in achieving safety, sustainability, and functionality targets while fostering collaboration across the value chain [8]. It focuses on providing a desirable function or service with the most cost-effective economic factors while considering sustainability and avoiding or minimising negative impacts on human health, society, and the environment from design to end-of-life [9].

Figure 1 Hierarchical SSbD principles (based on [1])

Within this approach, design principles are incorporated with concepts such as *green chemistry*, *green engineering*, *sustainable chemistry*, and *circularity* [9]. Its aim is to encourage the use of new scientific and technological knowledge while being easily adaptable to specific organisational needs and linking established methods and tools to foster safe and sustainable innovation. Although its implementation remains voluntary, it can help organisations prepare for future regulatory requirements and support compliance with existing safety and sustainability standards. As outlined in the introduction, the ANIPH SSbD assessment will follow the approach developed by the JRC [1] and entails two phases. The (re)design phase ensures that innovation is guided by clear goals and principles, addressing safety and sustainability challenges, and setting the stage for subsequent SSbD assessments to evaluate the effectiveness of the (re)design efforts. The safety and sustainability assessment phase examines the different components of safety, environmental, economic, and social aspects of the novel products, defining goals, scope, and indicators to ensure that the principles applied result in the best performance in terms of relevant indicators for the four mentioned dimensions. The safety and sustainability assessment ensures that a product is in

line with the design principles. In case the assessment indicates poor performance against the criteria, a redesign of the chemical or materials, its production process or its application is needed to improve the sustainability.

The ANIPH project requires specific adaptations of the standard SSbD approach to address the unique characteristics and challenges of advancing bio-based materials from TRL 2-3 to TRL 4-5 within a multi-stakeholder industrial context. The TRL progression from laboratory-scale proof-of-concept (TRL 2-3) to component validation in relevant environments (TRL 4-5) necessitates dynamic assessment methodologies that can accommodate rapidly evolving technical specifications, scale-dependent performance characteristics, and increasing data availability as the technology matures [9]. The framework emphasises early-stage market integration, incorporating preliminary techno-economic feasibility studies and stakeholder requirement mapping to ensure that sustainability assessments remain aligned with commercial viability objectives [1].

The ANIPH SSbD framework employs a comprehensive four-dimensional assessment approach that systematically evaluates the safety, and the environmental, social, and economic sustainability dimensions in an integrated manner to ensure holistic decision-making throughout the bio-based materials development process. This multi-dimensional strategy recognises that achieving true sustainability requires balancing potential trade-offs between dimensions, such as when environmentally beneficial bio-based materials may present higher initial economic costs or when safety improvements might increase environmental impacts through additional processing steps [1]. Once the technical solution becomes more mature and the expert group has been consulted (see subsection 4.4 for more detail), weighted multi-criteria decision analysis that incorporates stakeholder preferences and project-specific priorities will be carried out. As set out in the proposal, an expert group of 8-10 members will be established (i.e., health and social care representatives, healthcare and packaging industry representatives, plastic converter industry, consumer behaviour experts, bio-based processes expert, biodegradation and recyclability experts, circular economy experts, social impact assessment) to validate the SSbD assessment framework for the social and economic sustainability dimensions and improve functionality requirements of the products. As the public engagement strategy has not yet been implemented (D6.5 – M18), we propose to consult this expert group at a later stage, namely, to validate the social hotspots selected for the simplified social sustainability assessment based on the raw materials used for the ANIPH products and to establish the weighting of the different social and economic sustainability indicators for the multi-criteria decision analysis. To support integrated evaluation, the methodology will employ normalised scoring systems and aggregation methods that allow for meaningful comparison across dimensions, while maintaining transparency in how individual dimension performances contribute to overall sustainability ratings (see Section 9 for detail; [1]). The decision-making integration framework ensures that no single dimension dominates the assessment process, requiring minimum performance thresholds for each dimension while optimising overall sustainability outcomes. The scoring system will be built on the prioritised indicators of the developed evaluation matrix and summarised in a total score, further helping decision making based on minimum and maximum thresholds. This will allow us to rank the different options defined by their safety and sustainability performance while considering functionality. Decisions will be supported by using the scoring system, which will be integrated into the Evaluation & Decision tool as previously described.

4.2. (Re)design phase: Guiding principles

The concept of SSbD implies the (re)design of safe chemicals, materials, or products, minimising their emissions into the environment and the use of non-hazardous resources to reduce the negative impacts on human health and the environment [1]. As previously introduced, several principles support the integration of SSbD considerations during the design phase: 1) material efficiency, 2) minimisation of hazardous chemicals/materials use, 3) energy efficiency, 4) renewable sources, 5) prevention and avoidance of hazardous emissions, 6) reduction of exposure to hazardous substances, 7) end-of-life, and 8) consideration of the whole life cycle. Table 1 provides definitions for these principles.

Table 1 SSbD design principles (based on [1])

SSbD Principles	Definition
Material Efficiency	Incorporation of all the chemicals/materials used in a process into the final product or full recovery inside the process as to reduce the use of raw materials and waste generation.
Minimisation of Hazardous Chemicals/Materials Use	Preservation of product functionality while reducing or avoiding the use of hazardous chemicals/materials where possible.
Energy Efficiency	Minimisation of total energy use in the manufacturing process and/or along the supply chain needed to produce a given chemical/material.
Renewable Sources	Preserve resources via closed resource loops or the use of renewable or secondary material and energy sources.
Prevention and Avoidance of Hazardous Emissions	Application of technologies to minimise or avoid hazardous emissions or pollutants from being released into the environment.
Reduction of Exposure to Hazardous Substances	Elimination of exposure to hazardous chemicals where possible. Chemicals/materials that require extensive risk management should be avoided altogether. The best technology should be used to avoid exposure to hazardous substances over the life cycle.
End-of-Life	Design of chemicals/materials so that once they have fulfilled their function, they break down into products that are not hazardous to humans and the environment. Facilitation of chemical, material, or product reuse, waste collection, sorting, and recycling/upcycling.
Consideration of the Whole Life Cycle	Application of other SSbD principles while taking into consideration the whole life cycle from the supply chain of raw materials to the final product end-of-life.

These principles focus on the technical requirements and approaches leading to safety and environmental goals. However, the scope of ANIPH goes beyond these dimensions by also considering principles from social and economic sustainability as in our previous Horizon Europe projects [10], [11]. The latter are not addressed by these widely used SSbD principles. However, there is an initiative currently working on standardising common principles and assessment methodologies for a joint European SSbD approach that encompasses the work published by the JRC [1], [9], [12]. This initiative is under consultation and recognises the present need to develop

specific design principles and assessment tools to incorporate the economic and social sustainability dimensions into practice. More specifically, in ANIPH, the objective is to advance the new bio-based materials from TRL 2-3 to TRL 4-5. This constrains the economic assessment because TRL 4-5 is too far from the final product that will be sold [9]. Thus, the acknowledgment of the underdeveloped economic dimension in SSbD evaluation becomes particularly critical when operating at low TRLs, where benchmarking against commercialised products presents inherent methodological challenges. This gap becomes more pronounced at early development stages where emerging technologies lack the scale economies, production efficiencies, and market optimisation that characterise established commercial products. The development of frameworks and tools has become necessary to help organisations transition towards more sustainable practices, yet conventional economic evaluation methods often penalise early-stage innovations by comparing them against mature technologies. At TRLs 4-5, SSbD technologies are typically demonstrated at the laboratory or pilot scale, making direct economic comparisons with large-scale commercial alternatives inherently unfair and potentially misleading for decision-making. To address the identified gaps in the economic and social sustainability dimensions, ANIPH developed enhanced design principles. The proposed principles¹ are based on the work carried out in another European funded project (i.e., ViSS [11]). We will follow the terms harmonisation presented in the ViSS framework to ensure consistency of definitions, a common general understanding, and the terms normalisation for future inclusion in the ICT platform. As part of ViSS, we carried out a literature review and co-design/validation workshop to propose new sets of design principles, categories, aspects, and indicators for the social and economic sustainability dimensions.

SSbD dimensions include overarching principles. Categories – also called classes or groups – refer to thematic ensembles of the four dimensions (i.e., safety, environmental, social, and economic sustainability). Categories aggregate a set of aspects – also referred to as subcategories or impact categories. Aspects relate to relevant characteristics of categories. Indicators – also called criteria – are used at an operational level to perform the qualitative and quantitative assessment. Aspects entail one or more indicators. Figure 2 represents the hierarchical organisation of these concepts.

Principles > Categories > Aspects > Indicators

Figure 2 Hierarchical SSbD concept definition (taken from [1])

¹ Further details of the principles (*definitions, sources, link with indicators...*) are outlined in each dimensions' section.

4.3. Framework implementation

Although the initial ANIPH SSbD framework was developed under WP2, it will be further refined, and the assessment phase will be carried out in WP5 and WP11. Figure 3 illustrates the expected deliverables along with the sequential implementation that spans from framework development to comprehensive assessments.

Figure 3 Sequential implementation of working packages and their respective deliverables

Framework implementation follows a timeline that spans the whole project in line with the technical development achieved in other WPs. Implementation begins with the submission of the present document: the SSbD Framework (D.2.3) in WP2 at M9 (September 2025). It serves as a foundational milestone that enables subsequent assessment activities. WP5 (M10-M24) initiates the preliminary assessment phase through three deliverables: 1) data integration in ICT Platform tools (D5.1), 2) preliminary ANIPH safety assessment (D5.2), and 3) preliminary ANIPH sustainability assessment (D5.3). These assessments will be executed in parallel once sufficient material characterisation data becomes available, enabling early identification of potential safety or sustainability concerns that may motivate design modifications and selection of the parameters to be used in the assessments (i.e., functional unit). They will define the baseline against which the final evaluation will be compared, allowing us to assess product improvement at the end of the project, together with the comparison to established market benchmarks. WP11 (M25-M48) builds upon preliminary findings to conduct comprehensive final assessments, culminating in the final ANIPH safety (D.11.2) and sustainability assessment (D.11.3). Resource allocation timing is strategically aligned with technology maturation, with initial assessments scheduled to coincide with TRL 4 achievement and final assessments timed for TRL 5 validation. The expert group set up through the public engagement strategy (i.e., D6.5) which is due during M18 will be consulted through co-creation workshops to provide input regarding the scoring system for the social and economic sustainability assessments. One co-creation workshop is planned during WP5 (M12-M24), and another one is planned during WP11 (M25-M48).

Framework implementation establishes specific benchmark comparisons to ensure meaningful evaluation. For wound dressing applications, bio-based materials will be assessed against conventional polyurethane and polyurethane-based adhesive systems, while packaging will be

benchmarked against polyethylene terephthalate multilayers and cellulose with paraffin coating systems. This dual-benchmark approach will ensure that economic sustainability assessments can account for the performance and cost variation across different conventional material systems, thereby providing more robust and market-relevant evaluation outcomes despite the early TRL.

4.4. Assessment phase

In ANIPH, the assessment phase will help to identify the performance of newly designed or existing products further developed for each SSbD dimension. The goal of the continuous assessment is to ensure that their safety and sustainability performance improves during production, use, and/or end-of-life. This will be done through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for the environmental dimension, Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) for the social dimension, and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) for the economic dimension. In ANIPH, the assessment phase will comprise six steps carried out sequentially or in parallel (see Figure 4 for illustration):

Figure 4 Steps of the ANIPH SSbD assessment (adapted from [1])

For the scoring of products, the social and economic sustainability dimensions will follow the same scoring system as for the safety and environmental sustainability dimensions. This will enable

aggregation of the final scores for each dimension. The final assessment outcomes will be translated into a score between 0 (i.e., failing) and 4 (i.e., best possible performance). A score of 2 will be the passing score for each given indicator. Visualisation of the scores will be based on the JRC SSbD framework [1] and integrated into the ANIPH ICT platform (Deliverable 11.1). Figure 5 provides an overview of the ANIPH SSbD framework formulation and assessment.

Figure 5 ANIPH SSbD framework formulation & assessment (taken from [1])

The following sections will be devoted to the detailed description of the different methodologies that will be used in each of the steps (i.e., Section 5: Steps 1-3, Section 6: Step 4, Section 7: Step 5, and Section 8: Step 6).

5. Safety by Design and Safety Assessment

Incorporating safety factors into every stage of the development process for chemicals, materials, and products entails safety by design. This means selecting low-toxicity feedstocks, employing green production processes, designing for recyclability or biodegradability, and creating multifunctional products [9]. The safety assessment evaluates the potential risks associated with the chemical or material, considering its composition, degradation products, and end-of-life scenarios. AUA will assess both intentionally added substances (IAS) and non-intentionally added substances (NIAS). For IAS, their physicochemical properties will be linked to potential human and environmental hazards. This will be achieved by evaluating their toxicological and ecotoxicological profiles using in-silico machine learning models developed in Block 1, in compliance with national and EU regulations. NIAS will be experimentally identified and quantified using the following analytical techniques:

- Volatile compounds – Headspace Gas Chromatography Time-of-Flight (HS-GC-TOF)
- Semi-volatile compounds – Gas Chromatography Time-of-Flight (GC-TOF)
- Non-volatile compounds – High-Performance Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-MS)
- Specific migration testing

The hazard of detected NIAS will be assessed using quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models. If potential hazards are identified, AUA will apply quantitative structure–property relationships (QSPRs) to trace the origin of the NIAS—identifying precursor substances and process conditions responsible for their formation. Based on this, AUA will propose measures to prevent their generation or mitigate their impact.

5.1. Design phase

"By-design" in the SSbD criterion definition for chemicals, materials, and products refers to the next three aspects as defined by JRC [1]:

- Molecular design: Creating novel compounds and materials at the atomic level to tailor safer materials.
- Process design: Developing or improving production methods to make them safer and more resource-efficient, without changing the material's inherent properties.
- Product design: Designing end-use products to meet specific functions, including the selection of safer materials.

The ANIPH SSbD framework takes all these aspects into consideration. It is applicable for determining in which direction molecular design should go (including designing an optimal production procedure), but it is also intended to be useful to the engineers and scientists improving or inventing new production processes (re-design) for already existing chemicals and materials, and to product designers, when they must make decisions about other chemicals or materials to meet the functional demands of the products under development.

More specifically, as discussed in subsection 4.1, the ANIPH SSbD framework addresses two phases 1) Design (or re-design) phase where guiding design principles (listed in Table 1) are put forward to aid the design of safe chemicals and materials, and 2) Safety assessment phase (see below

Section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**) where the safety of the chemical(s) or material(s) under examination are evaluated. These two phases are iterative along the innovation process, i.e., a safety assessment is conducted from the early stages of development (see Figure 6).

As an example of potential integration between the SSbD and the innovation process, one of the most widely used approaches in this context is the phase-gate approach [13]. This iterative approach involves multiple iterations of a development phase by parallel evaluations of alternatives followed by a decision moment (i.e., gate), wherein the alternatives are filtered out based on a set of criteria applicable for that phase (see Figure 6). The SSbD assessment can be incorporated into this method by applying design principles along the development phase and conducting the SSbD assessment at the gate to confirm or revise the design accordingly. Nevertheless, the SSbD assessment must be modified considering the specific data availability along the TRLs of the innovative process, which determines the overall uncertainty of the SSbD assessment.

Figure 6 Relations between the innovation process, design principles, and the SSbD assessment (taken from [9])

The early stages of innovation are characterized by a lack of data regarding the physicochemical, functional, and toxicological properties of a molecule or material. At the same time, the explorable chemical space at that stage is at its maximum scope. Thus, molecular and material modelling and QSARs [14] supported by AI, also known as machine learning (ML), techniques are key enabling technologies during this first stage of design. In ANIPH, AI will support the SSbD concept in the early stages by generating information and data related to properties and characteristics that might not exist or be quantified at that point. Models like QSARs can provide output predictions for the potential toxicity and critical hazards of a chemical or material, supporting the identification of the most harmful and high-concern substances and determining whether the substances fulfil the SSbD criteria. Furthermore, solutions that qualify for a preliminary assessment stage can benefit from material flow and environmental fate analysis of the chemical or material considered, while being supported by QSARs and AI. It has to be highlighted, however, that the data necessary for the implementation of advanced data-demanding technologies such as AI and ML approaches

need to be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) to allow for the seamless integration and coupling of the envisaged computational tools [15].

5.2. Assessment Phase: Methodology

Safety risk assessment is a systematic process used to identify potential sources of harm (hazards), evaluate the likelihood and severity of their consequences (risks), and determine appropriate control measures to reduce or eliminate these risks [9]. According to the EFSA “A hazard is something that has the potential to harm you; risk is the likelihood that the hazard will cause harm”. The assessment phase comprises four steps: hazard, workers’ exposure during production, exposure during use, and life cycle assessment [1]. The assessment can be carried out either on newly developed chemicals and/or materials, or on existing chemicals or materials to improve their safety performance during production, use, and/or end-of-life. The steps are outlined below.

Step 1 - Hazard assessment of the chemical or material (intrinsic properties)

Step 1 looks at the intrinsic properties of the chemical or material to understand its hazard profile before further assessing the safety during use (see Figure 7). Figure 7 One of the reasons for implementing hazard-based criteria as a first step in the SSbD framework is that SSbD chemicals should be inherently safe to use in all kinds of uses in future life cycles. In this context the term 'by design' refers to intrinsic properties.

Figure 7 Illustration of chemical/material safety components captured in the proposed framework (taken from [1])

Coloured boxes mean that life cycle stage is covered. The red dot refers to the chemical/material under evaluation.

In the design phase, not all possible uses of a chemical or material are known, and they cannot always be predicted, therefore establishing a set of hazard-based criteria (human health, environmental, and physical hazards; see Table 2 is needed as it can guide the developers towards designing less hazardous chemicals or materials. Based on these considerations, the exposure aspects are not part of this first step but are considered in the other assessment steps.

Table 2 List of aspects (hazard properties) relevant for step 1 (taken from [1])

Group Definition	Human Health Hazards	Environmental Hazards	Physical Hazards
Includes the most harmful substances (according to CSS [7]), including substances of very high concern (SVHC) according to REACH Art. S7 [16]. These hazard properties form Criterion H1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carcinogenicity Cat. 1A and 1B - Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 1A and 1B - Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 1A and 1B - Endocrine disruption Cat/ 1 (human health) - Respiratory sensitisation Cat. 1 - Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 1. Including immunotoxicity and neurotoxicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic / very persistent and very bioaccumulative (PBT/vPvB) - Persistent, mobile, and toxic / very persistent and mobile (PMT/vPvM) - Endocrine disruption Cat. 1 (environment) 	
Includes substances of concern as described in CSS [7], defined in the Article 2 of SPI proposal [17] and that are not already included in Criterion H1. These hazard properties form Criterion H2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Skin sensitisation Cat. 1 - Carcinogenicity Cat. 2 - Germ cell mutagenicity Cat. 2 - Reproductive / developmental toxicity Cat. 2 - Specific target organ toxicity – repeated exposure (STOT-RE) Cat. 2 - Specific target organ toxicity – single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 1 and 2 - Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (human health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hazardous for the ozone layer - Chronic environmental toxicity (chronic aquatic toxicity) - Endocrine disruption Cat. 2 (environment) 	
Include other hazard classes not already part of Criteria H1 and H2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acute toxicity - Skin corrosion - Skin irritation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acute environmental toxicity (acute aquatic toxicity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explosives - Flammable gases, liquids, and solids

These hazard properties form Criterion H3.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Serious eye damage/eye irritation - Aspiration hazard (Cat. 1) - Specific target organ toxicity – single exposure (STOT-SE) Cat. 3 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aerosols - Oxidising gases, liquids, solids - Gases under pressure - Self-reactive - Pyrophoric liquids, solid - Self-heating - Emits flammable gas upon contact with water - Organic peroxides - Corrosivity - Desensitised explosives
--	--	--	--

The hazard assessment starts with gathering all relevant and available information. It is then followed by the hazard classification and assessment. The collected and generated data in Step 1 give an overview of the physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological properties of the chemical/material. From this information, we will provide a response to the formulated problem of hazard classification according to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulation (CLP) criteria. A first hazard identification issue for chemicals or materials is the amount of data needed in relation to their intrinsic properties to draw initial conclusions on their classification according to the CLP criteria. For new chemicals and materials at low tonnages, the available data may be quite limited. At the early stages of new molecular innovation, data is very scarce and NAMs data, such as from in vitro tests, and in silico models and tools (e.g., QSARs) are relevant means to support and guide the innovation process towards non-hazardous chemicals and materials since they provide information that is relatively economical to obtain. Another aspect which needs to be considered is that in silico tools usually build their prediction models based on pure chemical substances. Therefore, they may not be applicable to industrial substances or materials which can contain impurities or mixtures, which may not be well identified. The impact of impurities needs to be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. However, at the early innovation stages, there is a need to easily and reliably predict data to identify red flags as early as possible. As mixtures and materials are composed of substances, one way to identify these red flags is to choose the substance/component approach. This way, specifically at early innovation stages we will perform the assessment on individual components (substances) of a mixture or a material to address the data needs, using in silico tools. We will collect all available information, which can include:

- Information about the chemical/material identity
- Physicochemical data
- Non-testing data: i.e. data obtained with (Q)SAR models, grouping, read-across, weight of evidence etc.
- Testing data: including all in vitro and in vivo testing data, as available
- Human data, including epidemiological data, where available
- Any other data that may assist in identifying the presence or absence of hazardous properties. This information might be gathered from various sources such as regulatory and scientific

databases, scientific peer-reviewed literature and grey publications, internet searches and NAMs [18].

The generation of new data should follow a tiered approach as information becomes available, and as the need for new data is identified by the problem formulation. Data generation should start with the most conservative expected toxicological concerns, based on the structure and chemistry of the chemical or material. In a second tier, this information should be completed by looking for additional data and higher certainty levels with the use of *in silico* tools based on QSARs. QSARs can be an effective and efficient tool, especially for screening at early innovation stages, since they can identify red flags in a fast and economic way, and can help to correct the direction of the innovation before more resources are invested. This information can be completed with *in vitro* assays and *in vivo* studies in higher tiers, as more data is needed for the completeness of the assessment, and higher certainty is needed for a conclusive classification and assessment. The aforementioned classification criteria for substances and mixtures established by CLP regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 [16]) is used as reference and needs to be consulted for any detailed information such as: most harmful substances (H1), substances of concern (H2) and other hazard classes (H3).

Chemicals or materials that meet the requirements of a specific Step 1 criterion will be assigned a corresponding level that reflects the outcome of the hazard assessment for that criterion. In Step 1, four levels are defined (ranging from *Level 0* to *Level 3*) to rank chemicals accordingly and to integrate hazard-based evaluation results into the overall SSbD assessment:

- Level 0 – substances that fail hazard criterion H1 (e.g., those considered the most harmful).
- Level 1 – substances that satisfy H1 but fail H2 (e.g., those causing chronic effects and categorized as substances of concern).
- Level 2 – substances that comply with H1 and H2 but not H3 (e.g., those with other hazardous properties).
- Level 3 – substances that meet all safety criteria in Step 1.

We will use all the above information to determine tolerable maximum exposure levels for human populations, environmental compartments, and planetary boundaries. The derived no effect level (DNEL) and no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) represent maximum exposure levels for humans (e.g., workers, consumers) that should not be exceeded, with variations based on population sensitivity, exposure route, and scenario. Occupational exposure limits (OELs) serve a similar purpose for workers and are established by expert committees based on scientific data and exposure monitoring methods. However, not all substances have defined OELs. For the environment, the predicted no effect concentration (PNEC) is used to indicate the maximum safe concentration of a substance in specific environmental compartments such as soil, water, or air [9].

Step 2 - Human health and safety aspects in the chemical or material production and processing phase

In this step, the evaluation focuses on human health and safety aspects associated with the production and processing of the chemical or material. This encompasses the entire production chain, starting from raw material extraction (from natural resources) through manufacturing activities (e.g., substance synthesis, formulation, or mixing), and extending to recycling and waste

management (Figure 7b). The goal is to determine whether these processes pose risks to workers. The assessment considers both the hazardous properties of all substances involved (raw materials, intermediates, processing aids, etc.) and the likelihood of worker exposure.

Step 3 - Human health and environmental aspects in the final application phase

In this step, the evaluation addresses the hazards and risks associated with the final application of the chemical or material. The focus is on use-specific exposure scenarios and the potential risks that may arise from them. The goal is to determine whether the intended application poses threats to human health or the environment. This assessment integrates the hazard profile of the chemical or material (Step 1) with the likelihood of exposure to humans and the environment during its specific use (Figure 7c). To understand and estimate the exposure it is important to specify the use in which the chemical or material is utilised or applied. Any activity for which there is a potential for human or environmental exposure to a chemical or material is defined under REACH (European Parliament and the Council, 2006 [16]) as “use”.

The exposure and safety assessment start with the identification of the use case, which outlines scenarios of concern for human health and environmental safety. While the intrinsic properties of the chemical or material (hazard) remain the same during the entire life cycle, the exposure and therefore the risk will be specific to the use case. The use case explains how actors in the value chain interact with the chemical or material in its life cycle (the SSbD system). Relevant aspects for the exposure assessment and risk characterisation are summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Relevant aspects of the exposure identification and assessment (taken from [9])

OC: operational condition; RMM: risk management measure

Exposure scenario (ES) is a term introduced by REACH to describe the operational conditions and risk management measures (RMMs) that ensure that these uses are safe (i.e., the risk to human health and the environment is under control) during the life cycle of the chemical or material. The uses are described in Chapter R.12, [19] of the ECHA Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment, a system developed to facilitate chemical risk assessment and supply

chain communication. These descriptors have been also integrated in modelling tools such as the [tiered TRA](#) [20] tool developed by ECETOC and the [EUSES](#) tool [21] and are used as input parameters to derive exposure estimates. Besides describing the use, the operational conditions in which these uses take place need to be considered for the exposure estimation. The [ECHA Risk management measures and operational conditions](#) (Chapter R.13, [22]) provides supporting guidance on the most common types of use conditions having an impact on exposure. It includes an overview of operational conditions and risk management measures related to exposure of workers, consumers, and the environment.

The identification of the exposure scenarios, together with the description of the operational conditions/use conditions, provide the information to predict the exposure potential that can be minimised to ensure safe use by applying risk management measures. Exposure Models Working Group of the European Chapter (ISES Europe) produced a mapping of relevant available models and tools for exposure assessment. The mapping covers:

- [Workers](#) with tools and models for exposure assessment of occupational exposure due to handling of chemicals at workplaces (workers' exposure assessment (SWED)).
- [General population](#) (humans) with tools and models for exposure assessment of humans via the environment and for exposure assessment due to handling of chemicals by consumers (including different sub-populations), (consumers' exposure assessment (SCED)).
- [Environment](#) (ecosystem) with tools and models for exposure assessment of environmental compartments due to emissions to the environment (environment exposure assessment (SPERC)).

The [Use maps library](#) [23] currently includes also use maps developed by the European Plastics Converters.

The risk is characterised as a combination of the chemical or material hazard characterisation and the exposure assessment to human health and the environment (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 Aspects of the risk characterisation (taken from [9])

Depending on the approaches used, and the available data derived from both the hazard and exposure assessment, it will be also possible to perform the risk characterisation in a tiered approach, ranging from a qualitative (i.e., lowest tier) to a quantitative characterisation as data becomes available.

The following refinement options are available, depending on what we will consider to be the most efficient strategy.

- Improving the hazard information
- Improving the exposure information
- Improving information on operational conditions

- Improving information on risk management

In ANIPH, for developments under WP8, the safety of both product use and end-of-life scenarios will be thoroughly assessed. Regarding consumer exposure, CETEC will perform migration tests on the new packaging, and, based on hazards identified for IAS and NIAS characteristics of the produced materials, potential risks to consumers will be evaluated using exposure models, while AUA will assess possible adverse health effects. Compliance with medical regulations will be further demonstrated through in vitro tests on wound dressings. Potential environmental releases during product use will be analysed by AUA, considering the substance's transfer between phases and combining this information with ecotoxicity data to identify possible risks. At the end-of-life stage, AUA will conduct ecotoxicity tests simulating relevant environments with model organisms, following OECD standards, and combine these results with predictive assessments using the ANIPH-AI tool. This will include organism-level analyses to identify affected functions and ecosystem-level evaluations to assess impacts of biopolymers, additives, and intermediate degradation products, accounting for release rates. Specifically, freshwater and marine environments will be tested using the OECD 202 Daphnia sp., Acute Immobilisation Test [24] (endpoint: movement), while terrestrial toxicity will be assessed through plant growth (i.e., germination and growth endpoints) and earthworm responses. Finally, findings will be integrated into the ANIPH Evaluation & Decision Tool, enhancing traceability and ensuring alignment with other dimensions of sustainability (social and economic), thus enabling a holistic assessment in line with SSbD principles.

6. Environmental Sustainability by Design (eSbD) and eLCA

Environmental sustainability assessment plays a pivotal role in the ANIPH SSbD framework, providing a systematic method to identify, quantify, and mitigate potential environmental impacts associated with the production and use of the bio-based and biodegradable plastic products of interest for the project. This section presents the environmental dimension of the SSbD framework through two interconnected elements: the design considerations that inform the assessment process, and the methodological approach adopted for Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (eLCA). Together, these elements ensure that environmental sustainability is not only an evaluative outcome but also a guiding principle throughout the ANIPH products' life cycle development. The environmental assessment framework is structured around key impact assessment levels defined in the eSbD criteria proposed by [1], which include toxicity, climate change, pollution, and resources, ensuring alignment with the Environmental Footprint (EF) method and policy-relevant environmental priorities.

6.1. Design phase

For the environmental pillar specifically, the design phase acts as a critical filter that pre-conditions the validity and scope of the subsequent eLCA. By integrating environmental performance requirements during material and process selection, and by establishing clear system boundaries aligned with real-world scenarios (e.g., open environment biodegradability), the design phase ensures that the eLCA results are representative and actionable. It also supports the identification of environmental hotspots and informs the development of mitigation strategies, thereby enhancing the precision, relevance, and decision-support value of the environmental assessment.

Key design considerations for environmental sustainability assessment include:

- **Feedstock and process selection:** Opting for renewable and locally available feedstocks, such as agro-industrial residues, directly reduces reliance on fossil-derived raw materials and enhances resource circularity. In ANIPH, valorising waste streams for PHA production contributes to lowering the product's embodied energy and overall carbon footprint. Furthermore, low-energy bioprocessing techniques—such as non-sterile fermentations using halophilic bacteria for PHBV production—help minimise energy consumption and associated emissions during the production phase.
- **Material functionality and biodegradability:** The ability to tune polymer crystallinity and incorporate safe, biodegradable additives allows for customisation of biodegradation rates under specific environmental conditions. This is crucial for products like wound dressings and packaging that may be discarded in open environments. Ensuring materials degrade predictably and non-toxically supports the inclusion of realistic end-of-life scenarios in the eLCA model and helps avoid unintentional environmental accumulation of the relevant materials.
- **System boundaries and comparators:** Defining appropriate system boundaries is fundamental for meaningful LCA interpretation. For ANIPH, this involves cradle-to-grave modelling that

includes feedstock sourcing, biopolymer synthesis, product use, and disposal in relevant environmental settings (e.g., marine, soil). Equally important is the selection of appropriate comparators for benchmarking. In this context, ANIPH's wound dressings, and flexible packaging will be evaluated against conventional fossil-based counterparts—namely, polyurethane-based wound dressings and multilayer polyethylene/polypropylene flexible packaging.

- **Data availability and granularity:** The design stage must also consider the data infrastructure required for robust environmental assessments. Proactive identification of critical data needs during early-stage development helps target pilot studies (e.g., WP3, WP8) to generate primary LCI data. Additionally, the choice of materials and processes influences the availability of high-quality secondary data, shaping the uncertainty and sensitivity analyses in the eLCA.

Table 3 presents the environmental sustainability principles (i.e., the key environmental impact assessment levels as defined in [1]) next to their definition, and application in ANIPH.

Table 3 Environmental sustainability principles

SSbD Principles (based on environmental sustainability)	Definition	Application in ANIPH
Toxicity	Covers human toxicity (cancer and non-cancer) and ecotoxicity, potentially arising from production emissions or decomposition of substances	Selection of non-toxic, biodegradable additives and biopolymer formulations to avoid harmful degradation products; evaluation of freshwater ecotoxicity and chronic toxicity in eLCA.
Climate Change	Refers to global warming potential (GWP100), capturing the climate impact of GHG emissions over a 100-year time horizon.	Process-level GHG accounting for fermentation, material processing, and end-of-life scenarios; comparison of ANIPH prototypes to fossil-based counterparts to reduce carbon footprint.
Pollution	Encompasses ozone depletion, particulate matter, ionizing radiation, photochemical ozone formation, acidification, and eutrophication (terrestrial, freshwater, marine).	Inclusion of all EF-recommended impact categories in eLCA; development of materials that degrade safely without contributing to persistent environmental pollution.
Resources	Minimizing water, land, fossil resource, and mineral/metal usage to reduce environmental burdens; aligned with Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) guidance.	Use of agro-industrial and brewery residues as feedstocks; prioritisation of low-energy and resource-efficient production processes.

Areas of protection	Considers impacts on natural resources, ecosystem health, and human health.	Environmental assessment structured around EF midpoints and endpoints where applicable; integration of these impact pathways in SSbD classification.
Circularity	Promotes circular chemistry, minimalistic and safe molecular structures, and recyclability/biodegradability.	Emphasis on marine and soil biodegradability for end-of-life circularity; use of biologically recycled carbon from waste to support circular carbon loops.

6.2. Assessment phase: Methodology

The environmental sustainability assessment within ANIPH follows the SSbD framework proposed by the European Commission JRC, particularly the guidelines articulated in [1]. The assessment is based on a robust Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (eLCA; [3]) methodology, aligned with the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF; [4]) method.

The eLCA will quantify environmental impacts across the full life cycle stages of ANIPH products—spanning raw material sourcing, feedstock transformation, formulation, manufacturing, use-phase dynamics, and end-of-life management (e.g., recycling, biodegradation in marine or terrestrial environments). In accordance with Section 4 of this deliverable and the project’s temporal structure, this environmental assessment will be conducted in two distinct phases:

- A preliminary environmental sustainability assessment during WP5 (M10–24), focused on the first iteration of material prototypes developed within the ANIPH project. These include early formulations of wound dressings and flexible packaging derived from high-3HV PHBV and PHN polymers, with embedded antimicrobial and adhesive functionalities. This phase aims to evaluate the environmental performance of these material prototypes and their associated process chains—such as extrusion, compounding, 3D printing, and coating applications. The preliminary eLCA targets to generate early insights into environmental hotspots and material sensitivities, establish baseline impacts for key life cycle stages, and identify critical data gaps that require further experimental validation.
- A final environmental sustainability assessment in WP11 (M25–48), based on refined datasets obtained from pilot-scale implementations and optimized material formulations. These refined datasets will include improved life cycle inventory (LCI) data from upscaled fermentation and processing of PHBV and PHN polymers, pilot production of the PHBV films (CETEC), and enhanced integration of the Antimicrobial Additive (UGR) in product applications. This final eLCA also aims to incorporate updated energy consumption, material yield, and end-of-life degradation data specific to the final prototypes of wound dressings and flexible packaging. By integrating these advanced datasets, the final eLCA targets to deliver consolidated and high-confidence environmental performance profiles, directly supporting the validation of ANIPH’s SSbD strategy across the targeted application domains.

In addition to assessing final product systems, environmental evaluation will also be carried out for key ANIPH material components, including:

- CETBIO_PHBV_High_3HV – a semicrystalline poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) biopolymer with high 3-hydroxyvalerate content to enhance flexibility and processability. This material is developed by CETBIO using non-sterile fermentation of agro-industrial residues.
- TVB_mcl_PHA_PHN – an elastomeric medium-chain-length polyhydroxyalkanoate (mcl-PHA), primarily composed of poly(3-hydroxynonanoate), produced by TVB through microbial synthesis. It offers improved stretchability and resilience, targeting adhesives and water barrier coatings applications.
- UGR_Antimicrobial_Additive – a bio-based antimicrobial additive (probiotics cellulose) developed by UGR, designed to be incorporated into polymer matrices to confer antibacterial properties suitable for wound dressing applications, as alternative to conventional antibiotics, while maintaining biodegradability and biocompatibility.
- CETEC_PHBV_Films – packaging-grade films fabricated by CETEC using PHBV-based formulations and PHN based coatings and adhesives, optimized for mechanical strength, water barrier properties recyclability and biodegradation under controlled and open-environment conditions.
- UGR_PHBV_Wound dressings – bio-based and biodegradable wound dressings manufactured by UGR using PHBV based compounds, PHN based adhesives and probiotics cellulose, ensuring technical performance and biodegradation under controlled and open-environment conditions.

These components represent critical technological innovations in the ANIPH material platform and will be individually assessed to understand their environmental footprints, inform design optimisation, and guide their integration into final applications. These assessments aim to ensure that sustainability insights are available not only at the product system level, but also at the level of critical inputs and formulations, providing a layered and modular understanding of environmental performance across the ANIPH value chain.

To validate ANIPH's environmental claims, the eLCA will also include a comparative assessment of fossil-based counterparts. Specifically, polyurethane-based wound dressings, polyurethane based adhesives and multilayer polyethylene/polyethyleneterephthalate (PE/PET) or coated cellulose flexible packaging will serve as benchmarks. These comparators reflect standard industry solutions and will be modelled using the best-available secondary data sources and literature. The comparative analysis will adhere to principles of functional equivalence, ensuring that system boundaries, performance requirements, and service lifetimes are aligned across alternatives. This approach will allow the ANIPH consortium to quantify potential improvements (or trade-offs) in climate impact, resource efficiency, and end-of-life performance, offering a robust basis for SSbD decision-making and communication.

To ensure alignment with the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS; [7]) and the SSbD framework [1], the environmental impact assessment in ANIPH will be structured according to the Environmental Footprint (EF; [25]) method. The eLCA will cover a comprehensive set of impact categories relevant for evaluating safe and sustainable chemical and material systems, as proposed in [1] (see Table 4).

Table 4 Environmental impact categories assessed in ANIPH (adapted from [1])

Aspect CSS / LCA Assessment Level	Environmental Footprint Impact Category	Indicator	Unit
Toxicity	Human toxicity, cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	CTUh
	Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans	CTUh
	Ecotoxicity, freshwater	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems	CTUe
Climate Change	Climate change	Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq
Pollution	Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11eq
	Particulate matter / Respiratory inorganics	Human health effects associated with exposure to PM _{2.5}	Disease incidences
	Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure to ²³⁵ U	kBq ²³⁵ U
	Photochemical ozone formation	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOCeq
	Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AEac)	mol H+eq
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AEte)	mol Neq
	Eutrophication, aquatic freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg Peq
	Eutrophication, aquatic marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg Neq
Resources	Land use	Soil quality index aggregating biotic production, erosion resistance, mechanical filtration, and groundwater replenishment	Dimensionless
	Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation weighted water consumption)	m ³ water eq of deprived water
	Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sbeq
	Resource use, energy carriers	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil)	MJ

Data for the eLCA will be derived from both primary and secondary sources to support robust life cycle inventory (LCI) development across the four assessment domains: preliminary, final, building-block materials, and fossil-based comparators. Primary data will be collected from

production processes within WP3, WP4 and WP8, including: fermentation inputs and yields (e.g., substrate consumption, microbial growth, PHA recovery), polymer formulations and conversion processing (e.g., cast/blown extrusion, 3D printing, coating, etc.), material throughput rates, product formulation specifications, energy use per unit operation, water consumption, waste generation, and emissions monitoring (if available). This data will be obtained via direct measurements, mass and energy balances, and standardized templates provided to partners. Examples of primary data requirements to compile the LCA datasets of the foreground systems for three of the four assessment domains (i.e. preliminary, final and building-block materials) are provided in Table 5.

Table 5 Key flows and examples of primary data requirements to conduct LCA within ANIPH foreground systems

Flow category	Examples of primary data required	Foreground systems
Product outputs	Output mass or surface area (kg, m ²) of prototype wound dressings and flexible packaging (as well as possible co-products) for preliminary and final assessments; mass of materials (e.g., PHBV, PHN, additives, coatings, adhesives) and co-products; mass or surface area of fossil-based comparator products for achieving the same function	ANIPH wound dressings and packaging (preliminary and final) production processes; building block materials' production processes
Material and transport inputs from technosphere	Material formulations (e.g., biopolymers, additives, adhesives, coatings), intermediate chemicals, packaging, water usage, and transportation logistics (modes, distances) for all assessment domains	
Electricity and heat inputs from technosphere	Pilot-scale electricity use (type/source: grid mix, renewables), heating fuels (e.g., steam, natural gas) for polymer synthesis and processing	
Final waste outputs	Disposal fractions not entering circular routes: incinerated waste, landfill residues, expired or rejected production batches	
Waste outputs for further processing	Recyclable process scrap, biodegradable waste to composting/anaerobic digestion, treated wastewater discharged from pilot operations	

Secondary data will be sourced from recognized LCA databases such as Ecoinvent [26], Industry data [27], Carbon Minds [28] and Environmental Footprint [29], to model background processes including: energy production (national electricity mixes), transport logistics, supply chain emissions, and standard material production for fossil-based comparators (e.g., polyurethane, polyethylene, polyethylene terephthalate). When necessary, literature-derived LCI datasets will be used for emerging or underrepresented materials, with clear documentation of assumptions. To ensure alignment with the Environmental Footprint (EF) method, data quality will be evaluated using a pedigree matrix covering five quality indicators: reliability, completeness, temporal correlation, geographical correlation, and technological correlation. Each indicator will be rated

on a qualitative scale to generate overall uncertainty scores for foreground and background systems.

The time boundary for all eLCA assessments will be one year of operation. The system boundaries will follow a cradle-to-grave approach encompassing feedstock acquisition, material synthesis, processing, functional use, and end-of-life (including composting, biodegradation, and incineration scenarios as applicable). The functional unit will be defined by application domain to ensure comparability and tailored LCA modelling. Table 6 outlines the proposed functional units across the various environmental sustainability assessment domains reported in this section.

Table 6 Functional units across environmental sustainability assessment domains

Environmental Sustainability Domain	Functional Unit	Description
Preliminary Assessment (Wound Dressings)	Per unit of wound dressing	Delivers equivalent therapeutic function over a defined treatment period
Preliminary Assessment (Flexible Packaging)	Per square meter of packaging	Ensures equivalent mechanical protection and product shelf-life
Final Assessment (Wound Dressings)	Per unit of final prototype dressing	Incorporates updated formulations and performance profiles
Final Assessment (Flexible Packaging)	Per square meter of final prototype packaging	Reflects pilot-scale and commercial-ready configurations
Materials	Per kg of raw material	Assesses upstream environmental impacts of PHA polymers, additives, coatings, and adhesives
Fossil-Based Counterparts	Matched to functional equivalence of ANIPH alternatives	Ensures valid comparison by aligning on performance, durability, and use context

All analyses (i.e. ANIPH materials' LCA datasets and supply chain model compilation, life cycle inventory and life cycle impact assessment) will be carried out using LCA software tools such as SimaPro or OpenLCA. For life cycle impact assessment, EF-compliant impact assessment models will be employed. Special focus will be given to hotspot identification to guide redesign opportunities and process optimisations.

Interpretation of LCA results will follow a structured approach to support decision-making within the SSbD evaluation framework. In line with the criteria definition and evaluation system proposed in [1] for the structure of the framework for environmental sustainability assessment, a multi-indicator decision-support logic based on three key dimensions² will be applied for interpreting LCA results:

² The three dimensions—Magnitude of Environmental Impact, Relevance to Policy or Societal Concerns, and Improvement Potential—are distilled from Section 4.2.4 of the JRC framework [1], which emphasizes quantitative LCA results, alignment with EU policy priorities, and the potential for sustainability improvement. These have been operationalized to support transparent interpretation of eLCA outcomes within ANIPH's SSbD framework.

- **Magnitude of environmental impact:** This refers to the absolute and relative values of LCA impact indicators such as Global Warming Potential (GWP-100), acidification, or ecotoxicity as quantified using the EF method. It enables identification of environmental hotspots across the product life cycle and provides a numerical basis for comparing ANIPH materials with benchmark fossil-based alternatives.
- **Relevance of impact category to policy or societal concerns:** This dimension prioritizes impact categories that align with policy priorities (e.g., EU Green Deal [6], Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability [7]) and societal expectations. For example, climate change and microplastic generation are not only scientifically significant but also carry strong public concern and regulatory focus.
- **Improvement potential:** This criterion assesses whether meaningful reductions can be achieved through redesign, material substitution, or process optimisation. For ANIPH, this includes the flexibility to tailor polymer properties or modify fermentation parameters to reduce environmental burdens without compromising functional performance.

Benchmarking against fossil-based counterparts will involve calculating the percentage reduction in key environmental impact category indicators (e.g., GWP, resource depletion) achieved by ANIPH materials. Although the relevant scientific literature is scarce, threshold percentage values will be extracted, when possible, from the available scientific literature and policy targets (e.g., EF benchmarks, EU Taxonomy standards). In the absence of fixed thresholds, performance will be interpreted across normalized quintiles of impact intensity, as suggested in [1], allowing comparative ranking within the ANIPH material portfolio. This tiered system enhances interpretability by combining quantitative rigor with flexibility in data context, supporting a transparent classification into different levels of environmental sustainability. Thresholds will be suggested and validated during the final eLCA phase using sensitivity analysis and will support transparent interpretation and prioritisation of material alternatives. Finally, the eLCA findings will be integrated into the ANIPH Evaluation & Decision Tool, enhancing traceability and ensuring alignment with other dimensions of sustainability (economic and social), thus enabling a holistic assessment in line with SSbD principles.

7. Social Sustainability by Design (S-SbD) and S-LCA

Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines are critical to the understanding of factors conditioning social acceptance and to develop informed industry and policy recommendations. These disciplines are integrated into ANIPH to define the roadmap for identifying end-users' needs and to assess the social sustainability of the two proposed solutions (i.e., bio-based wound dressings and water barrier packaging) via qualitative and statistical analysis. Thus, the project will tackle their risks, safety, and environmental, social, and economic sustainability assessment throughout the whole product development process, in line with the SSbD framework and other social metrics. ANIPH's Specific Objective SO8 is *to ensure sustainability across ANIPH value chain*. To fulfil this objective, the assessment of the social sustainability of the solutions will primarily utilise the SSbD approach, with the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA; [5]) as central methodology, complemented with other social metrics.

ANIPH aims to contribute to a more socially sustainable design of novel chemicals, materials, and products. S-SSbD (social sustainability by design) for industrial processes as value chains may impact a wide range of social aspects such as social justice, the wellbeing of populations affected by changes in the ecosystem, worker welfare, worker and community health, political corruption, and fair treatment of workers among others. Although important, the social dimension of sustainability tends to be neglected compared to the environmental dimension [30]. Including it in the design phase of chemicals, materials, and products aims to protect individual and collective rights while maximising common welfare [31]. S-SbD can inform decision-making to design products that optimise positive social impact instead of causing social harm. The methodology involves the definition of complex criteria that help assess potential impacts in individuals or groups. However, there is no commonly agreed upon definition of social sustainability [32]. The following sections explain our approach to evaluating it, showing how social factors fit into the larger SSbD framework, and providing readers the necessary context.

7.1. Design phase

The main objective of S-SbD is to consider the social impact that products can have on individuals and groups throughout their life cycle. According to S-SbD, materials, chemicals, and products should maximise benefits for society, or at the very least not deteriorate welfare [5]. Social sustainability involves a wide range of stakeholders: the workers who produce the product, the community that can benefit or be negatively affected by its production, use, and disposal, the consumers, and the decision makers who can facilitate or hinder the production, use, or disposal of the product. As such, S-SbD implies considering several actors with possibly conflicting interests and the potential impact the product has on them, as well as defining acceptability thresholds [1]. Taking a holistic approach is key to carrying out S-SbD. As with other pillars of SSbD, the definition of principles that frame the design process is key.

We will follow Missimer's [33] five principles to support social sustainability when designing a new product. They are associated with the five stakeholder categories identified by the UNEP (i.e., workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers [5]) and because they link social sustainability principles with social aspects. The five principles that products should follow are outlined in Table 7. It integrates this social sustainability principles with the practical aspects identified in the S-LCA methodology, providing a structured approach to applying the principles within the specific context of ANIPH's biodegradable wound dressing and water barrier packaging.

Table 7 Social sustainability principles (based on [33]) and the ANIPH project

SSbD Principles (based on social sustainability)	Definition & Examples of Actions	Corresponding Social Aspects	Application in ANIPH
HEALTH: Health and Wellbeing	Avoidance of physical, mental, and emotional injury and illness across the value chain. <i>Action: Design products that minimise, and ideally avoid, exposure to hazards and integrate wellbeing considerations for all stakeholders. The product should minimise potential harm for the user.</i>	<i>Forced Labour; Working Hours; Health and Safety; Safe and Healthy Living Conditions; Secure Living Conditions; GHG Footprint; End-of-Life Responsibility; Affordability</i>	ANIPH will develop systems that reduce exposure to conventional polyethylene films, fossil-based paraffins, additives, and antibiotics for factory workers and humanitarian workers, as well as minimise occupational hazards through biodegradable formulations that eliminate the handling and disposal requirements of conventional plastics.
INFLUENCE: Stakeholder Influence & Participation	Foster meaningful participation of affected stakeholders in decision-making processes throughout product design and implementation. <i>Action: Implementation of inclusive design processes that integrate feedback from diverse stakeholders, in particular end users.</i>	<i>Social Benefits and Legal Issues; Wealth Distribution; Public Commitment to Sustainable Issues; Technology Development; Community Engagement; Local Employment; Feedback Mechanisms</i>	ANIPH will establish multi-stakeholder consultation workshops with consumers, the healthcare, packaging, plastic converter industries, health and social care representatives, public administration and procurers, and local communities to incorporate their perspectives in the iterative design of wound dressings, water barrier packaging, and an AI predictive system (software), creating solutions that address real-world needs and constraints.

<p>COMPETENCE: Competence Development</p>	<p>Contribution to skills enhancement and knowledge across the value chain. <i>Action: Design products that create opportunities for learning and competence development for workers, and local communities, and consumers. The production process should consider the training of workers and provide competence development.</i></p>	<p><i>Equal Opportunities / Discrimination; Workers' Rights; Fair Competition; Supplier Relationship; Intellectual Property Rights; Contributions to Economic Development; Technology Development; Access to Material Resources; Access to Immaterial Resources; Delocalisation and Migration; Local Employment; Secure Living Conditions</i></p>	<p>ANIPH will focus on facilitating knowledge exchange of best practices for the ANIPH solutions among end users. The project will document practical experiences from demonstrators for the wound dressings, the water barrier packaging, and the AI predictive system (software) with different relevant stakeholders to share lessons learned about optimal usage of the ANIPH solutions, supporting practical skill development through interactive knowledge transfer.</p>
<p>IMPARTIALITY: Equitable Value Distribution</p>	<p>Fair distribution of benefits and burdens across stakeholders and generations. <i>Action: Design systems that distribute value equitably throughout the value chain, particularly to vulnerable stakeholders.</i></p>	<p><i>Fair Salary; Equal Opportunities / Absence of Discrimination; Social Benefits, Legal Issues & Social Security; Workers' Rights; Sexual Harassment Prevention; Supplier Relationships; Corruption Prevention; Poverty Alleviation; Transparency; Affordability;</i></p>	<p>The ANIPH solutions will be developed with price points accessible to different scales of healthcare, humanitarian, and industrial operations, while quantifying potential economic benefits for end users.</p>
<p>MEANING-MAKING: Meaning-Making & Cultural Alignment</p>	<p>Support of creation of individual meaning and co-creation of common meaning, respecting diverse cultural contexts. <i>Action: Associate the organisation to a purpose that is understood and followed by workers. Design products that align with</i></p>	<p><i>Promoting Social Responsibility; Public Commitment to Sustainable Issues; Access to Immaterial Resources; Cultural Heritage; Community Engagement; Local Employment; Transparency</i></p>	<p>ANIPH will develop bio-based wound dressings and water barrier packaging that align with humanitarian workers' experience and knowledge while enhancing their sense of environmental stewardship.</p>

	<i>cultural values and enhance the meaning of humanitarian workers. Respect individual employee culture.</i>		
--	--	--	--

7.2. Assessment phase: Methodology – Social Life Cycle Assessment

This section proposes a set of criteria to assess the social sustainability of ANIPH products based on the S-LCA methodology and the project methodologies developed by some consortium partners for two past European research projects, Agro2Circular [10] and ViSS [11]. Given the low TRLs of the different ANIPH products at the start of the project and limited data related to material components, we propose a tiered approach which will start with a simplified assessment for the preliminary SSbD assessment (i.e., WP5) to evolve into an intermediate assessment and then a more complete assessment for the final SSbD assessment (i.e., WP11). For the preliminary assessment, the identification of social hotspots – processes, activities, or geographical locations along ANIPH’s product life cycles where a social issue (as positive or negative performance) and/or social risks is likely to occur – for the raw materials will be identified. These social hotspots will be considered as the innovation progresses and data for critical aspects will be collected or generated. Social hotspot analysis can be carried out with secondary data (i.e., sector or country-level data) available from databases and statistics that describe the likelihood that a social topic is relevant. Following the increasing availability of data and the definition of the innovation, an intermediate assessment will be carried out where primary and company-specific data will be prioritised over secondary data and life cycle actors increasingly engaged. The WP11 assessment will be carried out when the number of iterations of the intermediate level converge to provide data quality and availability. The full assessment will include all social aspects, dimensions, and indicators.

S-LCA is a framework developed and used to assess the social impact of goods and services throughout their life cycles [33]. Sustainable design involves the entire value chain of the product or service from raw material production to use and end-of-life and the effects of related activities throughout the whole life cycle. The framework for the assessment will reflect the social sustainability principles presented in the ‘Design phase’ section. As previously mentioned, the UNEP guidelines for the S-LCA of products [5] consider five stakeholder categories that match Missimer’s principles [33]: workers, value chain actors, society, local community, and consumers. These categories are used in the present assessment.

The stakeholder category WORKERS corresponds to eight aspects that consider:

- whether the organisation uses **forced labour**;
- whether practices concerning **wages meet legal requirements**;
- whether the **number of hours effectively worked** is in accordance with the International Labour Organization (ILO) standards and time and/or financial compensation is planned and provided to workers when overtime occurs;
- how **equal opportunity practices** are managed and the presence of **discrimination** in the opportunities offered to the workers;

- the **rate of incidents** and the **status of prevention measures and management practices** within the organisation;
- whether and to what extent the organisation provides **social benefits and social security** to workers;
- whether the organisation complies with **freedom of association and collective bargaining standards**; and
- whether the organisation creates or tolerates working conditions in which **sexual harassment** occurs, and to what extent actions are successful in preventing it.

The stakeholder category VALUE CHAIN ACTORS corresponds to five aspects that consider:

- whether the organisation's **competitive activities are conducted in a fair way and in compliance with legislation** preventing anti-competitive behaviour, anti-trust, or monopoly practices;
- whether the organisation promotes **social responsibility** among its suppliers and through its own actions;
- whether the organisation considers the potential **impacts of its procurement and purchasing decisions on other organisations**, and acts with due diligence to avoid or minimize any negative impact (ISO 26000);
- whether the organisation respects **intellectual property rights**; and
- the extent to which the **value created** in the production process is **distributed in an equitable way** across all actors of the value chain.

The stakeholder category SOCIETY corresponds to five aspects that consider:

- whether the organisation has **public commitments to sustainability issues**;
- the extent to which the organisation, product, or service contributes to **economic development**;
- whether the organisation participates in **joint research and development** for efficient and environmentally sound technologies;
- whether the organisation has implemented **appropriate measures to prevent corruption** and whether there is evidence that it has engaged in corruption; and
- presence of **activities such as strategies, action plans, and investment to reduce societal poverty** at different geographical levels undertaken by the organisation itself or linked with the product life cycle.

The stakeholder category LOCAL COMMUNITY corresponds to nine aspects that consider:

- the extent to which the organisation respects, and works to protect, provide or improve access to **local material resources and infrastructures** (including adaptation of the value chain to favour the local economy);
- the extent to which the organisation respects, and works to protect, provide or improve access to **local immaterial resources** (including adaptation of the value chain to favour the local economy);
- whether the organisation contributes to **delocalisation, migration, or involuntary resettlement** within communities and whether populations are treated adequately;
- whether the organisation respects **local cultural heritage** and recognises that all community members have a right to pursue their cultural development;

- the extent to which the organisation impacts **community safety and health**;
- whether the organisation includes **community stakeholders** in decision-making processes and the extent to which it engages with the community as a whole;
- the role of the organisation in directly or indirectly affecting **local employment**; and
- how the organisation impacts the **security of local communities** with respect to the conduct of private security personnel and how it interacts with state-led forces; and
- the organisation's **greenhouse gas emissions**.

The stakeholder category CONSUMERS corresponds to five aspects that consider:

- the existence and scope of systematic efforts to address **consumer health and safety** across the organisations involved in the life cycle of a product or service;
- the effectiveness of management practices to support **consumer feedback**;
- whether the organisation communicates on all issues regarding its product or service and social responsibility in a **transparent way**, including traceability);
- whether there are management efforts to address the social impacts of **product or service end-of-life**; and
- whether the product or service is **affordable and competitively priced** in line with the market and considering the price of hazardous alternatives.

Table 8 relates aspects of the different stakeholder categories to the social sustainability principles outlined in the previous subsection to monitor that all social sustainability principles are included in the assessment and that the products comply with them.

Table 8 Relations between social sustainability aspects and principles (based on [33])

Stakeholder Categories		Workers						Value Chain Actors					Society				Local Community						Consumers												
Social Sustainability Aspects		Forced Labour	Fair Salary	Working Hours	Equal Opportunities / Discrimination	Health and Safety	Social Benefits and Social Security	Workers' Rights	Sexual Harassment	Fair Competition	Social Responsibility	Supplier Relationships	Intellectual Property Rights	Wealth Distribution	Public Commitment to Sustainability	Contribution to Economic Development	Technology Development	Corruption	Poverty Alleviation	Access to Material Resources	Access to Immaterial Resources	Delocalisation and Migration	Cultural Heritage	Safe and Healthy Living Conditions	Community Engagement	Local Employment	Secure Living Conditions	GHG Footprint	Health and Safety	Feedback Mechanism	Transparency	End-of-Life Responsibility	Affordability		
Social Sustainability Principles	Health	✓		✓		✓																	✓				✓	✓							
	Influence					✓							✓	✓		✓								✓	✓				✓						
	Competence				✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓			✓	✓	✓			✓	✓									
	Impartiality		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓					✓	✓			✓	✓				✓	✓			✓				✓	
	Meaning-Making									✓					✓				✓		✓		✓		✓	✓				✓					

Table 9 summarises the indicators we propose for the implementation of the S-LCA assessment (based on A2C [10], ViSS [11], JRC [1], UNEP [5], PSILCA [34], and CEFIC [35]). Importantly, the simplified SSbD assessment (i.e., WP5) focusing on social hotspot analysis will allow us to test the feasibility of indicators. As such, some social indicators may be discarded for the full assessment. To highlight the relevance of the S-LCA, the relationships between aspects and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG; [36]) are included. Selected indicators are based on a systematic integration of empirical findings from European research (i.e., A2C [10] and ViSS [11]) and established methodological frameworks. The selected indicators were further informed by social sustainability literature from the bioplastics sector [37], [38], [39], ensuring comprehensive coverage of relevant social dimensions while maintaining applicability in the specific context of wound dressings and water barrier packaging.

Table 9 Indicators for the S-LCA assessment and their relations to SDGs

Stakeholder Category	Indicators	Aspects	Related SDGs ³
Workers	- Employment terms - Forced labour	Forced Labour [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	3, 8, 10
	- Living wage, per month - Minimum wage, per month - Average wage, per month	Fair Salary [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	1, 2, 3, 4
	- Flexibility - Full-time staff	Working Hours [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	3, 8
	- Gender equality - Equal opportunities policy	Equal Opportunities / Discrimination [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	1, 4, 5, 8, 10
	- Occupational safety measures - Injury frequency rate	Health and Safety [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	2, 3, 6, 8
	- Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	Social Benefits, Legal Issues, Social Security [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA]	3, 8, 9, 11
	- Trade union density - Collective bargaining agreement	Workers' Rights [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	8, 10, 16
	- Sexual harassment incidents reported	Sexual Harassment [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	8
Value Chain Actors	- Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	Fair Competition [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	12
	- Promotion of corporate social responsibility - Supplier audit	Social Responsibility [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	12

³ For more information on the SDG: [THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development](#)

	- Supplier communication relationship	Supplier Relationships [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	12
	- Fair price definition	Wealth Distribution [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	1, 8, 10
	- Number of intellectual property rights infringements	Intellectual Property Rights [ViSS, JRC, CEFIC]	9, 12, 16
Society	- Presence of public documents on sustainability issues	Public Commitment to Sustainability [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	12, 17
	- Total taxation per capita	Contribution to Economic Development [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA]	1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 9
	- Technology transfer - Investments in technology development/transfer	Technology Development [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	4, 9, 17
	- Corruption	Corruption [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA]	16
	- Poverty alleviation programme	Poverty Alleviation [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	1, 2
Local Community	- Environmental management system	Access to Material Resources [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	9, 12
	- Community education initiatives	Access to Immaterial Resources [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	4, 12
	- Immigrant workforce rate - Procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	Delocalisation and Migration [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	9, 10, 11
	- Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage	Cultural Heritage [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	11
	- Promotion of community health	Safe and Healthy Living Conditions [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, PSILCA, CEFIC]	3, 6
	- Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation - Number of meetings with community stakeholders	Community Engagement [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	11, 12
	- Local workforce - Spending on local suppliers	Local Employment [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	8
	- Security complaints by the community	Secure Living Conditions [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	3, 16

Consumers	- Labelling - Complaints - Presence of a Quality or Product Safety Management System	Health and Safety [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC, CEFIC]	2, 3, 12
	- Presence of a feedback mechanism	Feedback Mechanism [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	12
	- Organisational communication transparency	Transparency [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	9, 12
	- Internal management systems	End-of-Life Responsibility [A2C, ViSS, UNEP, JRC]	12, 15
	- Price in comparison to market equivalent	Affordability [ViSS, JRC, CEFIC]	10, 12

Assessment of the selected indicators will be conducted according to an SSbD score (0 to 4) or SSbD level (pass or fail) when scoring is not possible (for more information on the scoring system see Section 4 and Section 9). It will be done using secondary data when available and consulting experts when data is not available.

7.3. Assessment phase: Methodology – Acceptability & Awareness

Complementing the S-LCA, to be conducted in WP5 (ANIPH SSbD assessment and enabling conditions - 1), and WP11 (ANIPH SSbD assessment and enabling conditions - 2), specific quantitative and qualitative social sciences and humanities (SSH) methodologies will be systematically applied to analyse social acceptability factors. This approach contributes to International Labelling System (ILS), since one of ANIPH's core objectives is to understand the factors leading to the BBpPs acceptance and the standards required for successful market adoption. Acceptability refers to the way stakeholders perceive and adopt ANIPH solutions (i.e., PHA wound dressings and water barrier packaging), including both usability and end-user acceptance. This multidimensional concept is essential to ensure practical implementation and market success. Awareness refers to individual and community environmental consciousness, which is crucial for influencing behavioural changes that support sustainability and create conditions that favour receptivity towards bio-based innovations.

ANIPH evaluation framework integrates technology acceptance theory with environmental psychology principles, recognising that successful innovation adoption requires alignment across technical performance, social acceptance, and environmental consciousness dimensions [40].

Table 10 outlines BBpPs acceptability assessment framework:

Table 10 BBpPs acceptability assessment framework

Acceptability (of BBpPs)	Evaluation methods	Target indicators
Industry, entrepreneurs and companies' acceptability: Profitability, market share, return on assets [41]	<i>Primary data collection:</i> Interviews and focus groups; Ad hoc questionnaire tailored to business context; <i>Secondary analysis:</i> Literature revision of industrial adoption patterns; Market analysis	Industry acceptability enhancement: Enhanced entrepreneurs and companies' acceptance of BBpPs and circular economy business models (+12%-15% ⁴ , 20-25% ⁵)
Consumers and public procurers' societal acceptability: Focus on social acceptance dynamics, product preferences, value alignment, information needs.	<i>Mixed-Method Evaluation:</i> In-depth interviews exploring consumer preferences and purchase behaviours Focus groups examining social dynamics and peer influence systems Open-ended questionnaires on product attributes (appearance, design, functionality, overall satisfaction Willingness to Pay (WTP) analysis Analysis of the relation of personal values taken at community-based level and acceptability in terms of purchase and WTP Analysis of the available information about traceability and impact	Social (consumers: healthcare professionals, citizens and public procurers) acceptance improvement: Improved social acceptability at local and community levels and Improved liking of BBpPs (+25%-35% ⁶ , +40-45% ⁷); Increased WTP (+4% ⁸ , +15% ⁹)

ANIPH will implement a comprehensive stakeholder identification and engagement framework targeting relevant actors across the healthcare value chain. The evaluation incorporates diverse perspectives from project partners, expert advisory groups, and target stakeholder representatives engaged through the integrated public engagement strategy (WP6, WP12).

To evaluate awareness of pro-ecological worldview of end-users and other relevant stakeholders, the revised New Ecological Paradigm scale (NEP; [42]) will be used. Through fifteen items, it quantifies five conceptually interrelated facets of an ecological worldview: reality of limits of

⁴ Estimates at the end-of the project based on literature review

⁵ Estimates for for the mid-term, measured over the baseline (oBL) that will be established at the beginning of the project implementation

⁶ Estimates at the end-of the project based on literature review

⁷ Estimates for for the mid-term, measured over the baseline (oBL) that will be established at the beginning of the project implementation

⁸ Estimates at the end-of the project based on literature review

⁹ Estimates for for the mid-term, measured over the baseline (oBL) that will be established at the beginning of the project implementation

growth (items 1, 6, 11), antianthropocentrism (2, 7, 12), fragility of nature's balance (3, 8, 13), rejection of exceptionalism (4, 9, 14), and possibility of an eco-crisis (5, 10, 15). Respondents will be asked to rate their (dis)agreement with each statement using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. It is important to note that the dimensionality of the NEP has been criticized, but we will use this scale for descriptive purposes to explore endorsement of a pro-ecological view. After correcting for item directionality, the mean and standard deviation of each dimension will be calculated. Additional, other metrics could be considered in later stages of the project (i.e., Ecologically Conscious Consumer Behavior (ECCB) scale [43]). Table 11 summarises the dimensions, the tools and methods used, the components we will assess, and the corresponding stakeholder we will survey as part of the social sustainability assessment.

Table 11 Summary of the dimensions, tools and methods, components, and stakeholders involved in the social sustainability assessment

Dimension	Tools & Methods	Component Assessed	Target Stakeholder Group
Sustainability & Circularity	SSbD	Integration of SSbD principles across product life cycle	All stakeholder categories
	S-LCA	Social changes generated	ANIPH organisation, industry partners, workers, consumers, value chain actors.
Acceptability	Ad-hoc questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups	Understanding attitudes towards both ANIPH wound dressings and packaging and their origin, properties, and disposal	Consumers, healthcare professionals, public procurers
	Interviews and focus groups	Economic viability assessment	Industry partners, entrepreneurs, companies
	Ad-hoc questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups	Functionality/usability of ANIPH products	ANIPH end users, healthcare professionals
	Ad-hoc questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups	Purchasing behaviour analysis and market fit assessment	Humanitarian workers, procurement professionals
	Ad-hoc questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups	Co-determining factors: how well ANIPH products meet users' needs and areas of improvement	All end-user categories
Awareness	NEP[42]	Environmental awareness	All stakeholder categories

This comprehensive methodology ensures that acceptability assessment provides robust evidence for understanding the human and market factors determining successful implementation of environmentally responsible and technically sound bio-based healthcare innovations, while contributing valuable insights to labelling system development.

8. Sustainability Costing by Design (cSbD) and LCC

Economic aspects are crucial when evaluating different options within the SSbD framework (e.g., the chemicals or additives appropriate for a specific processing step). Economic sustainability comprises different aspects crucial to the product design phase, including techno-economic feasibility, operational costs, and monetisation of environmental externalities. Nevertheless, there is currently no universally agreed-upon definition of economic sustainability: the interpretation and application of this concept vary across contexts [44]. This section outlines the economic dimension of the SSbD assessment methodology for the ANIPH project. First, we present an outline of the proposed design principles. Finally, we present the assessment phase.

8.1 Design phase

The design guiding principles useful to optimise the economic sustainability of ANIPH wound dressings and water barrier packaging presented in this subsection are exploratory, as the JRC [1] has not included the economic dimension in its framework. They are based on the proposal elaborated within the ViSS project [11] that draws from different sources including the definition of economic sustainability [1], the list of SSbD design principles, and related empirical evidence [45], [46].

Economic sustainability is understood as more than profitability. It encompasses a range of aspects that are integral to product design. In the context of SSbD, economic sustainability is related to the assessment of techno-economic feasibility and operational costs relating to the different decisions made during the product design phase. Resource efficiency, longevity, and circular economy principles are considered to ensure that the products promote long-term economic well-being. Life cycle aspects, cost effectiveness, resource efficiency, and social responsibility need to be balanced so that products contribute to the environment and society while also meeting economic objectives. Within the SSbD framework, economic sustainability is a guiding principle for making decisions that align with broader safety, sustainability, and responsible product development goals. Table 12 presents economic sustainability principles as proposed in the ViSS project next to their definition, corresponding economic aspect, and application in ANIPH.

Table 12 Economic sustainability principles (based on [9])

SSbD Principles (based on economic sustainability)	Definition	Corresponding Economic Aspect	Application in ANIPH
Cost Efficiency	Minimisation of product cost to reduce production costs by optimising both fixed and variable costs, including material costs.	Product Cost; Market-Related Criteria; Profitability Analysis	ANIPH will optimise PHA sustainable antimicrobial additive formulations, adhesives and coatings for wound dressings and water

	<i>Action: Set a minimum selling price for the product that equalises discounted costs and benefits.</i>		barrier packaging to reduce material costs while maintaining performance.
Resource Optimisation	Minimisation of expenses associated with the acquisition of materials via efficient material usage and waste treatment practices. <i>Action: Efficient energy and water consumption via measures that reduce energy and water costs during manufacturing, leading to more sustainable processes like electricity, heating, and cooling.</i>	Product Cost; Life Cycle and Externality Costs; Profitability Analysis	ANIPH will implement this principle by exploring synthetic sugar (i.e., from the agrifood industry) and yeast residues (i.e., from the brewery industry) as feedstock for PHA production, creating circular resource flows. Moreover, ANIPH will implement studies to reuse the by-products of the PHBV and PHN manufacturing processes. Circular design of manufacturing processes will be studied.
Equipment Life Cycle Management	Minimisation of expenditures associated with equipment over the life cycle, including acquisition and depreciation costs. <i>Action: Prioritise the procurement of environmentally friendly and energy-efficient equipment.</i>	Product Cost; Profitability Analysis	For ANIPH's development from TRL 2-3 to TRL 4-5, we propose exploring equipment that could potentially support the scaling process. This would require careful assessment of current partner capabilities and potential additional investment needs.
Installation and Operational Efficiency	Optimisation of installation costs and operational processes to minimise ongoing labour and maintenance costs. <i>Action: Design wound dressings and water barrier packaging for compatibility with existing medical devices. Create solutions with optimal degradation timelines in case of inadequate or non-existing waste management facilities.</i>	Product Cost; Profitability Analysis	ANIPH wound dressings and water barrier packaging will be designed for compatibility with existing medical devices to minimise adoption barriers. They will feature optimal degradation timelines in case of proper or inexistent waste management facilities.
Human Resources	Consideration of social impact by ensuring fair	Product Cost;	ANIPH will quantify potential labour benefits

	<p>wages and reasonable working hours in the calculation of labour costs. <i>Action: Ensure fair compensation across all stages of the value chain.</i></p>	Profitability Analysis	through improved worker health due to reduced exposure to hazardous conventional additives.
Environmental Management	<p>Monetary valuation of environmental impact in the product or process design to address issues of pollution, resource depletion, and ecosystem disruption to design products that minimise negative environmental impact throughout their life cycle. <i>Action: Quantify economic benefits of improved terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem health and biodiversity.</i></p>	Life Cycle and Externality Costs; Market-Related Criteria	In ANIPH, we will monetise specific environmental benefits like reduced waste management costs for health care operations, absence of soil remediation costs from microplastic pollution, and increased economic benefits due to improved soil health.

8.2 Production process and LCC calculations

The economic feasibility assessment of ANIPH wound dressings and water barrier packaging is based on the life cycle cost (LCC) methodology, applied to the entire production chain of biodegradable wound dressings and water barrier packaging. The production process includes the following main stages:

1. PHBV and PHN Ranges Manufacturing (WP3 & WP8)
 - Maximisation of upstream and downstream processes for PHBV and PHN range production to programme biodegradation
 - Safe formulation and compounding of PHBV and PHN with programmed biodegradation
 - Predictive assessment of materials processability and biodegradability
 - Optimisation of PHBV and PHN safe and sustainable compounding
 - Small-scale manufacturing of wound dressing and packaging with programmed biodegradation
2. Preliminary Manufacturing of Materials for Wound Dressing and Packaging (WP4)
 - Development of probiotics@cellulose additives (i.e., alternative to antibiotics)
 - Manufacturing of PHBV- and PHN-based adhesives and coatings
 - Properties and biodegradation predictive assessment of ANIPH medical additives, adhesives, and coatings
3. Safe and Sustainable Biodegradation and Recyclability Validation (WP9)
 - ANIPH experimental biodegradation studies
 - Validation of packaging recyclability

4. Demonstration of the ANIPH Solution (WP10)
 - Scaling up of ANIPH materials
 - Demonstration of ANIPH and validation in real environments

Each stage is carefully designed to maintain both the functional performance required in health care settings and the eco-friendly credentials dictated by current environmental standards. More details on material processes can be found in Section 6.

8.3 Assessment phase: Methodology

The economic sustainability indicators taken from the different frameworks reviewed by the JRC can be grouped into four aspects: product cost, profitability, life cycle cost and externality cost, and market-related criteria [1]. ANIPH will follow the same classification:

- **Product cost:** The production cost comprises the total expenditure associated with the manufacturing of the product, accounting for both fixed and variable costs. It comprises the purchase cost, which is the market price of required materials. Carrying out a comprehensive cost calculation is crucial for financial analysis. The minimum product selling price, defined as the lowest price at which the product achieves a net-zero present value, is a key indicator. It ensures that the revenue generated by the sale of the product covers both costs and benefits, facilitating a break-even point in practice.
- **Profitability:** Profitability analysis involves an assessment of a product's financial performance and viability by analysing several financial metrics like net present value, added value, payback period, and financial profit. It aims to evaluate the owner's major financial interest in the income formation process of a product (i.e., balance between income generation and income distribution).
- **Life cycle cost and externality cost:** Life cycle and externality costs account for a product's total economic impact throughout its life cycle, including direct production costs and externalities such as environmental emissions.
- **Market-related criteria:** Market-related criteria comprise indicators related to market dynamics and consumer behaviour influencing economic decisions, such as willingness to pay.

In Table 13, each economic aspect is related to indicators along with their definition/method of calculation. Those indicators were selected from the ViSS project [11], the JRC framework [1], and related literature. Similar to the social sustainability assessment, we will first carry out a simplified SSbD assessment (i.e., WP5) due to the limited availability and quality of data linked to the ANIPH material components and low solution TRLs which will eventually evolve into a full SSbD assessment (i.e., WP11). During the assessment phase, economic indicators will be progressively integrated and may be refined or discarded due to limited data availability or quality or operational constraints encountered during the project life cycle. For example, value chain disruptions may prevent accurate measurement of certain production costs or pilot-scale manufacturing may yield insufficient data for statistically significant market projects.

Table 13 ANIPH LCC indicators and related aspects and definitions (based on [9])

Economic Aspect	Indicators	Definition / Method	Data Source	
Product Cost / Price	Purchase cost of raw materials (<i>inputs</i>)	€, price of the chemical/raw material in the market	Primary data (obtained from ANIPH partners: CETEC, CETBIO, AUA, TVB, UGR)	
	(Total) production costs (<i>other inputs and operating costs</i>)	Water		€, (total) production costs including fixed and variable costs [47]
		Energy – Electricity		
		Energy – thermal energy		
		Energy – natural gas		
		Carbon dioxide to air		
		Transport		
		Equipment (capital costs)		
		Installation		
		Labour cost		
Maintenance				
Minimum product selling price (<i>product price in the market</i>)	€, minimum price of the product at which the cost and benefits break even, leading to a net-zero present value [47]			
Profitability	Normalised added value [-]	The added value is normalised by dividing it by the product sale price [48]	Primary data (obtained from ANIPH partners: CETEC, CETBIO, AUA, TVB, UGR)	
	Profitability	No specific method / metric		
	Net present value	€, difference between the present value of cash inflows and of cash outflows, discounted over a set period of time [49]		

	Added value	The added value is the difference between product value and total input costs [48]		
	Payback period	Time needed to reimburse the investment (calculated by dividing the amount of investments by the annual cash flow) [49]		
	Financial profit	€, profits earned from commercialising products [49]		
Life Cycle Cost and Externality Cost	Externality cost	€, monetised environmental and health impact linked with environmental emissions, worker safety, health protection, and land eco-remediation [50]	Primary data (obtained from ANIPH partners: CETEC, CETBIO, AUA, TVB, UGR); secondary data (market benchmark)	
	Cost of waste treatment	Waste costs		€, cost of waste treatment (e.g., cost of recycling a solvent or treating the emissions that would be released in the air)
		Waste treatment emission costs		
		Recycling treatment costs		
	Environmental taxes	€, amount of taxes levied on activities considered harmful to the environment		
Environmental subsidies	€, amount of payments or financial support given to promote activities that have a positive environmental impact			
Market-Related Criteria	Willingness to pay	€, price that individuals are willing or able to pay for a reduction in risks/negative impact	Primary data (obtained from ANIPH partners: CETEC, CETBIO, AUA, TVB,	

		to their health and the environment	UGR); secondary data (market benchmark, third party data gathering)
	Product performance	Performance compared to conventional alternative products	

The assessment of economic performance requires company-specific data such as revenues and cash flow.

Table 14 relates economic sustainability aspects and their respective indicators to the economic principles defined within the ANIPH SSbD economic assessment framework. The assessment phase provides insights into the product's sustainable economic performance and enables an assessment of whether product design aligns with defined principles.

Table 14 Relations between economic sustainability aspects and principles (based on [9])

Economic Sustainability Aspect	Product Cost			Life Cycle and Externality Costs					Market-Related Criteria		Profitability Analysis						
	Purchase cost	Total production cost	Minimum selling price	Externality cost	Cost of waste treatment	Environmental taxes	Environmental subsidies	Externality cost	Willingness to pay	Product performance	Normalised added value	Profitability	Net present value	Added value	Payback period	Financial profit	
Economic Sustainability Principles	Cost Efficiency	x	x	x						x	x		x	x			
	Resource Optimisation	x	x			x						x		x	x		x
	Equipment Life Cycle Management	x												x	x	x	
	Installation and Operational Efficiency		x									x			x		
	Human Resources	x	x									x	x		x		
	Environmental Management				x	x	x	x	x		x						

The LCC methodology is complemented by the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) and the Cost Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) methods to provide additional perspectives. CBA assesses project viability by comparing costs over time to monetary benefits. Within the CBA framework, we will analyse the Net Present Value (NPV) as main indicator. Other parameters may be explored along project implementation to reach a more nuanced understanding of the economic feasibility of ANIPH. To get NPV, a discount rate (X) is applied to cash flows (CF) across time (t) as per the following formula:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1 + X)^{t-1}}$$

where:

X : discount rate

t (period): typically measured in years

CF_t (cash flow at time t): net cash flows (inflows minus outflows) at each t . When benefits exceed costs, it is positive. When costs exceed benefits, it is negative. It includes all project monetary flows.

$(1 + X)^{t-1}$ (discount factor): this factor decreases the value of future cash flows to account for the temporal value of money

If NPV is positive, the project achieves profitability. We will define cash flows comprehensively (i.e., initial R&D development, pilot production costs, testing and certification costs, IP protection) and benefits (i.e., potential market value, environmental cost avoidance, performance advantages, potential policy incentives). We will also establish the discount rate for commercial benefits. NPV metric is useful to calculate monetary incentives to pursue safety and sustainability targets. However, there are also non-monetary reasons to pursue these which will be demonstrated by complementary SSbD LCC metrics. Complementarily, the CEA method will evaluate whether potential benefits justify further investment to reach higher TRLs. It captures the relationship between costs and specific benefits within a defined timeframe.

9. Evaluation and support decision tool

ANIPH will integrate an Evaluation and Support decision tool into its ICT Platform, developed by CETEC in WP2. The objective of this software is to translate SSbD results into actionable insights for decision-making across the full value chain. The ANIPH Evaluation and Decision Tool is a platform for partners to make decisions based on the SSbD evaluation matrix. The tool is designed to help partners achieve project objectives for the safety and sustainability of materials and products by providing quantitative scoring value for each functional unit. This can be used to compare ANIPH's products and production methods to others on the market.

The Evaluation and Decision Tool digitalises the SSbD framework, allowing partners to assess and quantify the safety, sustainability, economic viability, and social impact of the ANIPH solution. It functions as a decision-making support system, ensuring that ANIPH wound dressings and packaging meet high safety and sustainability standards.

This module will comprise four integrated elements designed to provide comprehensive SSbD evaluation capabilities:

1. Evaluation matrix

The evaluation matrix will capture the different specifications across the four SSbD dimensions through carefully selected indicators, providing quantitative performance (e.g. kg CO₂ eq/kg for emissions, €/kg for production cost...) for predetermined functional units¹⁰ (e.g. 1 kg of PHBV, 10 biodegradable packaging...). Following the JRC methodological guidance [9], the matrix will employ the Reference Scale Approach (RSA), which evaluates performance and risk based on predefined reference points with specific thresholds and intervals for each assessment level, rather than attempting to establish direct cause-effect chains. The RSA methodology is particularly suitable for ANIPH's innovation context as it handles incomplete data, common in early innovation stages, allows comparison of alternatives with different data quality and accommodates both quantitative and qualitative indicators.

2. Scoring system

The tool uses a scoring system where the outcome of an evaluation for each aspect is translated into a score from "fail" to "best possible performance", thus translating evaluation outcomes into standardized scores using a uniform 5-point ordinal scale (0-4) across all criteria. This scoring system will be uniform for all criteria, to enable easy combination and visualization in figures or tables, being Level 4 "excellent performance with very low risk", Level 3 "good performance with low risk", Level 2 "acceptable performance with medium risk", Level 1 "poor performance with high risk" and Level 0 "unacceptable performance or very high risk failing SSbD standards".

Example of Reference Scale (reference level) for the indicator in the Social Dimension: Worker safety – Injury frequency rate [9]

- Level 4 (Very Low Risk): 0-7.5 per 100k employees
- Level 3 (Low Risk): 7.5-15 per 100k employees
- Level 2 (Medium Risk): 15-25 per 100k employees
- Level 1 (High Risk): 25-40 per 100k employees

¹⁰ Functional units will be defined once the technical development of the products is more advanced.

- Level 0 (Very High Risk): >40 per 100k employees

The scoring methodology integrates across all four SSbD assessment dimensions: hazard assessment (Step 1) evaluating intrinsic chemical properties against CLP classification criteria, safety assessment (Steps 2-3) examining risk characterization ratios and exposure scenarios, environmental sustainability assessment (Step 4) comparing LCA results against reference products or benchmarks, and socio-economic assessment evaluating social performance and supply chain risks.

Drawing on both ANIPH requirements and ViSS project learnings, the following parameters will be established collaboratively with the expert group and consortium members:

- Pass/ Fail criteria: the purpose is to set an “early warning” for chemicals and materials (or products) that do not pass the “most harmful substances (H1), Substances of concern (H2) and other hazard classes (H3)” criteria. The “Automatic Fail” will be considered when:
 - Any Score 0 in critical safety indicators (Step 1 H1 substances, Steps 2-3 RCR >2.0)
 - Any Score 0 in regulatory compliance indicators
- Data quality: an initial proposal of this parameter would be to adjust the score based on the confidence in data depending on the source, incorporating a data quality through confidence flags and structured data hierarchy (primary company data → secondary industry data → proxy data → expert judgment). For example,
 - Actual company accident records → Certainty = 1.0
 - Industry average for your sector → Certainty = 0.8
 - Estimations based on similar processes → Certainty = 0.6
 - Expert consultations → Certainty = 0.4
- Weighting Methodology: Weights will be determined through expert consensus and stakeholder consultation, considering ANIPH's specific context and product development priorities

Individual indicator scores are aggregated using weighted averages with transparent data quality considerations, ensuring decision-making transparency while accommodating iterative development from laboratory to commercial scale.

3. Data collection and integration

Data will be collected from the different assessments in WP5 & WP11 incorporating four data types with decreasing preference order: primary company-specific data (gathered through structured questionnaires and interviews), secondary industry/country averages from established databases, proxy data from similar processes when direct data is unavailable, and expert judgment for qualitative assessments where quantitative data is lacking.

Learning from ViSS project experiences, particular attention will be paid to establishing clear benchmarking frameworks early in the process to avoid methodological inconsistencies that could necessitate structural platform modifications later in development

4. User interface

The interface will include dashboards that display charts, rankings, alerts, and tables to facilitate the understanding and analysis of results. The UI's design focuses on simplicity and clarity, adapting to various screen sizes. Building on ViSS platform developments, the interface will provide dynamic tracking of SSbD scores with automatic updates as new functional units are

assessed, ensuring continuous monitoring capabilities throughout product development phases. The Evaluation and Decision Tool goes beyond a simple scoring tool by integrating complex evaluation methodologies, data input from multiple sources, and a user-friendly interface, all within an iterative development process to ensure its relevance and accuracy throughout the life of the ANIPH project. This tool will be one part of the ICT Platform, an essential part that will be interconnected with the Traceability Tool to link a product traceability to its SSbD assessment and to the Public Tool to export assessment summaries for stakeholders and consumers, enhancing transparency and acceptance.

Through this module, ANIPH ensures data-driven decision-making that balances safety, environmental sustainability, economic viability, and social impact — fully aligned with the SSbD methodology for PHA biopolymer development at TRL 4–5. Further information will be provided in D2.6 and integrated in the final ICT Platform deliverable (D11.1, M47).

10. Conclusions

The SSbD framework presented in this deliverable is the final output of Task 2.3 to evaluate the produced bio-based wound dressing and packaging designed according to SSbD principles. To ensure full adherence to SSbD methodology, establishing a robust assessment framework is imperative. Deliverable 2.3 represents the initial phase in validating compliance with the four dimensions of the SSbD approach to provide a holistic sustainability evaluation of these novel solutions, the first step towards objective 8 *to ensure Safe & Sustainable ANIPH BBpPs and create an enabling framework (MS2, MS14, MS9, MS11, MS15)*.

As presented along the framework, the implementation of the SSbD framework remains in its early stages, particularly for novel bio-based and biodegradable polymers and plastics value chains where data scarcity and methodological gaps persist. The ANIPH SSbD framework successfully integrates four key sustainability dimensions—safety, environmental, social, and economic—to provide a holistic evaluation of the materials throughout their life cycle. This approach goes beyond conventional SSbD frameworks by systematically incorporating social and economic sustainability assessments from the early stages of development. The practical integration of the last two dimensions remains limited, with specialised challenges emerging for biodegradable materials that require assessment of biodegradation safety, rates, and additive compatibility. ANIPH addresses these operationalisation challenges through an innovative approach that combines AI-enhanced safety evaluation tools, validated LCC and S-LCA methodologies, and a blockchain-enabled ICT platform ensuring transparent value chain communication and traceability.

The framework leverages existing EC guidelines and methodologies, such as the JRC framework, to establish clear and measurable indicators for safety and environmental dimensions. This foundation provides a robust and validated basis for evaluation, including methodologies like Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF). While a preliminary set of principles and indicators has been proposed for the social and economic dimensions, we acknowledge a lack of universally agreed-upon definitions and the early TRL of the ANIPH technologies. The validation and weighting of these indicators will be pursued in later project stages through consultation with an expert group.

The SSbD framework serves as the foundation for the project's Evaluation and Decision Support tool and ICT platform. By using a normalized scoring system, it ensures a consistent evaluation across all work packages and dimensions, enabling transparent, data-driven decision-making throughout the project's life.

In summary, Deliverable D2.3 represents a crucial first step, establishing the methodological groundwork for assessing the safety and sustainability of ANIPH's novel bio-based products.

11. References

- [1] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials. LU: Publications Office, 2022. Accessed: Dec. 15, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/487955>
- [2] E. Abbate et al., 'Operationalization of the safe and sustainable by design framework for chemicals and materials: challenges and proposed actions', *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 245–262, Mar. 2025, doi: 10.1093/inteam/vjae031.
- [3] International Organization for Standardization, 'Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework'. ISO, July 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/37456.html>
- [4] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., 'Understanding Product Environmental Footprint and Organisation Environmental Footprint methods.', Publications Office, LU, 2022. Accessed: Sept. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/11564>
- [5] United Nations Environment Programme, 'Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of products', United Nations Environment Programme, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/guidelines-social-life-cycle-assessment-products>
- [6] European Council - Council of the European Union, 'European Green Deal', European Council - Council of the European Union, Feb. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/european-green-deal/>
- [7] European Commission, 'Chemicals strategy for sustainability', European Commission, Oct. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/8ee3c69a-bccb-4f22-89ca-277e35de7c63/library/dd074f3d-0cc9-4df2-b056-dabcacfc99b6/details?download=true>
- [8] Mohd Fahrul Hassan, M. Z. M. Saman, Safian Sharif, and Badrul Omar, 'Methodology for Sustainable Product Design: A Review and Direction of Research', 2011, doi: 10.13140/2.1.3689.9840.
- [9] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: methodological guidance. LU: Publications Office, 2024. Accessed: Sept. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>
- [10] Community Research and Development Information Service, 'TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR', European Commission, Oct. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101036838>
- [11] Community Research and Development Information Service, 'Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications', European Commission, Sept. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081931>
- [12] European Commission. Joint Research Centre., Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators, and tools. LU: Publications Office, 2022. Accessed: Apr. 22, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/879069>
- [13] R. G. Cooper, 'The Stage-Gate Idea to Launch System', in *Wiley International Encyclopedia of Marketing*, 1st edn, J. Sheth and N. Malhotra, Eds, Wiley, 2010. doi: 10.1002/9781444316568.wiem05014.

- [14] European Commission. Joint Research Centre. Institute for Health and Consumer Protection, Review of QSAR models and software tools for predicting acute and chronic. LU: Publications Office, 2010. Accessed: Sept. 04, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2788/60766>
- [15] M. D. Wilkinson et al., 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Sci Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 160018, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
- [16] European Commission, 'Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency'. Dec. 18, 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2006/1907/oj/eng>
- [17] European Commission, 'COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS On making sustainable products the norm'. Mar. 30, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52022DC0140>
- [18] F. Sewell et al., 'New approach methodologies (NAMs): identifying and overcoming hurdles to accelerated adoption', *Toxicology Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, p. tfae044, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1093/toxres/tae044.
- [19] European Chemicals Agency, Ed., Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment: Chapter R.12: use description, version 3.0 - December 2015. Helsinki: ECHA, 2015. doi: 10.2823/001435.
- [20] European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals, 'Targeted risk assessment (TRA)'. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecetoc.org/tools/tra-main/>
- [21] European Chemicals Agency, EUSES - European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances. (2019). [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/support/dossier-submission-tools/euses>
- [22] European Chemicals Agency, Ed., Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment: Risk management measures and operational conditions (Chapter R.13) (24/10/2012). Helsinki: ECHA, 2015. doi: 10.2823/001435.
- [23] European Chemicals Agency, 'Use maps'. [Online]. Available: <https://echa.europa.eu/csr-es-roadmap/use-maps/use-maps-library>
- [24] OECD, Test No. 202: Daphnia sp. Acute Immobilisation Test. in OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 2. OECD, 2004. doi: 10.1787/9789264069947-en.
- [25] European Commission, 'Understanding Product Environmental Footprint and Organisation Environmental Footprint methods', JRC129907.
- [26] Ecoinvent Association, 'Ecoinvent Database Version 3.10', Ecoinvent. [Online]. Available: <https://ecoinvent.org/ecoinvent-v3-11>
- [27] SimaPro, 'Industry Data LCA Library', SimaPro. [Online]. Available: <https://simapro.com/products/industry-data/>
- [28] Carbon Minds, 'Life Cycle Inventory Database for Chemicals and Plastics', Open LCA. [Online]. Available: <https://www.openlca.org/carbon-minds-chemical-database-2024-update>
- [29] European Commission - Joint Research Centre, 'Environmental Footprint (EF) database v3.1'. [Online]. Available: <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EF-node/>
- [30] A. M. Ly and M. R. Cope, 'New Conceptual Model of Social Sustainability: Review from Past Concepts and Ideas', *IJERPH*, vol. 20, no. 7, p. 5350, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ijerph20075350.
- [31] M. Traverso, 'Methodological Sheets for Subcategories in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) 2021 - Life Cycle Initiative', United Nations Environment Programme, 2021, [Online].

- Available: <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/library/methodological-sheets-for-subcategories-in-social-life-cycle-assessment-s-lca-2021/>
- [32] A. H. Rasouli and Dr. A. Kumarasuriyar, 'The Social Dimension of Sustainability: Towards Some Definitions and Analysis', *JSSPI*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2016, doi: 10.15640/jsspi.v4n2a3.
- [33] M. Missimer, 'Social Sustainability within the Framework for Strategic Sustainable Development', Blekinge Institute of Technology, Karlskrona, Sweden, 2015. Accessed: Mar. 31, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:bth-10464>
- [34] K. Maister, C. Noi, A. Ciroth, and M. Srocka, 'PSILCA v.3 Database Documentation'. Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://psilca.net/>
- [35] The European Chemical Industry Council, 'Safe and sustainable by design: A guidance to unleash the transformative power of innovation'. Mar. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://cefic.org/resources/safe-and-sustainable-by-design-a-guidance-to-unleash-the-transformative-power-of-innovation/>
- [36] L. Scherer, P. Behrens, A. De Koning, R. Heijungs, B. Sprecher, and A. Tukker, 'Trade-offs between social and environmental Sustainable Development Goals', *Environmental Science & Policy*, vol. 90, pp. 65–72, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.envsci.2018.10.002.
- [37] A. Di Bartolo, G. Infurna, and N. T. Dintcheva, 'A Review of Bioplastics and Their Adoption in the Circular Economy', *Polymers (Basel)*, vol. 13, no. 8, p. 1229, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3390/polym13081229.
- [38] S. H. Mousavi-Avval, K. Sahoo, P. Nepal, T. Runge, and R. Bergman, 'Environmental impacts and techno-economic assessments of biobased products: A review', *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 180, p. 113302, July 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2023.113302.
- [39] S. Kakadellis, Ž. Muranko, Z. M. Harris, and M. Aurisicchio, 'Closing the loop: Enabling circular biodegradable bioplastic packaging flow through a systems-thinking framework', *Cleaner and Responsible Consumption*, vol. 12, p. 100183, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.clrc.2024.100183.
- [40] L. D. S. Nascimento, J. R. Da Rosa, A. R. Da Silva, and F. M. Reichert, 'Social, environmental, and economic dimensions of innovation capabilities: Theorizing from sustainable business', *Bus Strat Env*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 441–461, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1002/bse.3506.
- [41] A. K. Moser, 'Thinking green, buying green? Drivers of pro-environmental purchasing behavior', *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 167–175, May 2015, doi: 10.1108/JCM-10-2014-1179.
- [42] M. Anderson, 'The New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) Scale', *The Berkshire Encyclopedia of Sustainability: Indicators and Research Methods for Sustainability*, 2012, [Online]. Available: <https://umaine.edu/soe/wp-content/uploads/sites/199/2013/01/NewEcologicalParadigmNEPScale1.pdf>
- [43] I. TILIKIDOU, I. ADAMSON, and C. SARMANIOTIS, 'The measurement instrument of ecologically-conscious consumer behaviour', *New Medit*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 46–53, 2002.
- [44] W. D. N. S. M. Tennakoon and M. P. N. Janadari, 'Measuring Economic Sustainability: Are we doing it Right?', *SL J. Soc. Sci. Hum.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–30, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.4038/sljssh.v2i1.53.
- [45] P. Antwi-Afari, S. T. Ng, and J. Chen, 'Developing an integrative method and design guidelines for achieving systemic circularity in the construction industry', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 354, p. 131752, June 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131752.

- [46] K.-H. Robèrt et al., 'Strategic sustainable development — selection, design and synergies of applied tools', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 197–214, June 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0959-6526(01)00061-0.
- [47] A. Al Ghatta, J. D. E. T. Wilton-Ely, and J. P. Hallett, 'From sugars to FDCA: a techno-economic assessment using a design concept based on solvent selection and carbon dioxide emissions', *Green Chem.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 1716–1733, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D0GC03991H.
- [48] P. C. Narváez Rincón, J. Serna, Á. Orjuela, and M. Camargo, 'Sustainability assessment for chemical product and process design during early design stages', in *Towards Sustainable Chemical Processes*, Elsevier, 2020, pp. 3–41. Accessed: Apr. 26, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/B9780128183762000016>
- [49] R. L. Smith, G. J. Ruiz-Mercado, and M. A. Gonzalez, 'Using GREENSCOPE indicators for sustainable computer-aided process evaluation and design', *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 81, pp. 272–277, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.compchemeng.2015.04.020.
- [50] M. Govind Kharat, S. Murthy, S. Jaisingh Kamble, R. D. Raut, S. S. Kamble, and M. Govind Kharat, 'Fuzzy multi-criteria decision analysis for environmentally conscious solid waste treatment and disposal technology selection', *Technology in Society*, vol. 57, pp. 20–29, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.techsoc.2018.12.005.

